

**FORMULATION STUDIES OF RIFAMPICIN-LOADED SOLID LIPID
MICROPARTICLES**

BY

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2008/159120

**DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL TECHNOLOGY AND INDUSTRIAL
PHARMACY**

FACULTY OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA NSUKKA

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Approval page

This is to certify that this project carried out by Okeke Uchechukwu Chukwudi with registration number 2008/159120 was dully supervised and has been approved for the award of Bachelor of Pharmacy (B. Pharm.) degree in the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Nigeria Nsukka.

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Dedication

This work is dedicated first to the Almighty God who through his infinite mercies have supported me in all the stages of the preparation of this challenging project, it is also dedicated to my Dad and Mum who are the chief financiers of my academics and to my siblings who are the beneficiaries of this marvellous work.

I also dedicate this work to those interested in research that will help solve human practical problems.

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Okeke Uchechukwu Chukwudi

Abbreviations

cm	: centimetre
DSC	: Differential scanning calorimetry
EE	: Encapsulation efficiency
%^{w/w}	: percentage weight / weight
GRAS	: generally recognized as safe
hrs	: hours
<i>Irw</i>	: <i>Irvingia wombolu</i> fat
LBDDS	: lipid-based drug delivery systems
mg	: milligramme
ml	: millilitre
pH	: Negative logarithm of hydrogen ion concentration
P90H	: Phospholipon 90H
RMP	: Rifampicin
Rpm	: Revolutions per minute
SD	: Standard deviation
SLMs	: Solid lipid microparticles
TB	: Tuberculosis
UV	: Ultra violet
µm	: Micrometre
°C	: degrees centigrade
g	: gram
µg	: microgram
w/v	: weight/volume
θ	: Angle of repose

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Abstract

Rifampicin (RMP) is a major component in fixed dose combination therapy for the treatment of tuberculosis. RMP has low solubility and high permeability with high dose and hence it is classified as class II drug in Bio-pharmaceutics Classification System (BCS). RMP has poor and variable bioavailability because of its poor solubility, acid decomposition and drug and food interaction. In this study, an attempt was made to improve the solubility and thus eliminate the variability in the bioavailability of rifampicin by formulation as solid lipid microparticles (SLMs). Phospholipon 90H and *Irvingia wombolu* fat based SLMs of RMP was prepared by hot melt homogenisation method. Prepared SLMs were evaluated for its particle size and morphology, drug loading capacity, drug content, encapsulation efficacy, thermal behaviour, percentage yield, *in-vitro-in vivo* drug release and stability in simulated gastric fluid. The *in vitro* release studies of all SLMs were carried out in SIF, pH 6.8 and phosphate buffer pH 7.4 up to period of 12 h. Surface morphology revealed mono-dispersed, smooth and spherical microparticles; the particle size was in the range of 28 - 57 μm . The encapsulation efficiency of drug loaded microparticles was high and found in the range of 82.9 - 91.6 %. Differential scanning calorimetric studies confirmed the compatibility of drug with lipids and that formulation process altered the crystalline nature of RMP. Stability studies in simulated gastric fluid (SGF) indicated that low percentage decomposition of 7.6 % and 14.3% was achieved hence SLMs improved the stability of drug in stomach. The prepared SLMs in all the batches had a higher sustained-release effect than the market brand. The order of drug release retardation in both media was $P3 > P2 > P1$ as observed in case of LM 1:2. Rifampicin-loaded SLMs in SIF, pH 6.8 gave higher rate of drug release when compared to release in phosphate buffer, pH 7.4. However, in phosphate buffer there was more retarded release. The release mechanisms studied showed that microparticles had mixed mechanisms of release with diffusion controlled and first-order release models as the predominant mechanism of release in all the batches. The *in vivo* findings revealed that the SLMs batches exhibited their absorption peak at 3 h; however, these SLMs maintained constant plasma concentration up to 18 h. For the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), rifampicin-loaded SLMs were very effective and retained their bioactivity. The results obtained from the present investigation concluded that RMP loaded microparticles are suitable for developing oral sustained release dosage forms of RMP that can prevent acid decomposition and provide better biopharmaceutical properties. SLMs of rifampicin offers an attractive means of multi-particulate systems which can be filled in standard size gelatine capsules or compressed into tablets as oral sustained release dosage forms.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction and literature review

1.0 Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the major infectious diseases worldwide and its incidence is increasing particularly in association with AIDS pandemic (Harries *et al.*, 2001; Satish *et al.*, 2010). The four major drugs rifampicin (RMP), isoniazid (INH), pyrazinamide (Z) and ethambutol (E) are used widely as first line treatment of TB (Peloquin, 1993). Among these, INH, Z and E belong to the class I (highly soluble and permeable) of biopharmaceutical classification system whereas RMP is a class II drug (low soluble/highly permeable). Due to the low solubility, RMP (solubility 2.5 mg/ml, log p 1.086, pKa 4.96±0.7) has poor bioavailability in both fixed and single dose formulations (Panchagnula *et al.*, 2004). The reason for low bioavailability of RMP are changes in the crystalline nature, interaction with excipients, degradation in gastro-intestinal tract, variability in absorption and metabolism, its pH dependent solubility, etc. (Agrawal *et al.*, 2002; McIlleron *et al.*, 2002). Bioavailability problem of RMP is cause for the poor therapeutic outcomes including failure of therapy and drug resistance. TB chemotherapy is complicated by the need for multi-drug regimens given over long periods, patient noncompliance and the development of multi-drug resistant strains (MDR) (Panchagnula *et al.*, 2004). Poor patient compliance to the required long period of administration is one single most common reason for failure of TB therapy (Shishoo *et al.*, 2001).

The foregoing peculiar properties make it imperative to develop suitable drug carrier systems that will increase bioavailability and improve drug delivery. Many different drug carriers can be used depending on the route administration, the chosen drug properties and the intended release profile. Solid lipid microparticles (SLMs) were

developed in early 1990s and have since been considered to be promising drug carrier systems, especially with a view to give the incorporated active substance an improved dissolution hence increased bioavailability (Jaspert *et al.*, 2005; Pilaniya *et al.*, 2011). The present investigation was aimed to develop RMP loaded solid lipid microparticles (SLMs) that can prevent not only acid decomposition, but eliminate variability in bioavailability.

1.1 Drug delivery system (DDS)

A drug delivery system (DDS) is defined as a formulation or a device that enables the introduction of a therapeutic substance into the body and improves its efficacy and safety by controlling the rate, time, and place of release of drugs in the body (Jain, 2008). This process includes the administration of the therapeutic product, the release of the active ingredients by the product, and the subsequent transport of the active ingredients across the biological membranes to the site of action. The term therapeutic substance also applies to an agent such as gene therapy that will induce *in vivo* production of the active therapeutic agent (Verma *et al.*, 2001).

The concept of drug delivery system has emerged to minimize the toxic side effects of drug, to broaden their application, to expand modes of their administration and to solve absorption problems. The twentieth century has witnessed a remarkable growth in drug development and the newly developed drugs are mostly lipophilic compound with poor aqueous solubility, which limits their efficacy and bioavailability. Solubilization, encapsulation, and delivery of these drugs using lipid based and biocompatible systems are likely to furnish better absorption, by way of lower dose, reduced frequency of administration, and improved therapeutic efficacy (Pate *et al.*, 2008).

In the past few decades, considerable attention has been focused on the development of novel drug delivery system (NDDS). The NDDS should ideally fulfil two

prerequisites: firstly, it should deliver the drug at a rate directed by the needs of the body, over the period of treatment, and secondly it should channel the active entity to the site of action. Conventional dosage forms including prolonged release dosage forms are unable to meet none of these. Novel drug delivery system attempts to either sustain drug action at a predetermined rate, or by maintaining a relatively constant, effective drug level in the body with concomitant minimization of undesirable side effects. It can also localize drug action by spatial placement of controlled release systems adjacent to, or in the diseased tissue or organ; or target drug action by using carriers or chemical derivatization to deliver drug to particular target cell type (Biju *et al.*, 2006; Seema *et al.*, 2012).

1.1.1 Characteristics of an ideal DDS

Ideal DDS should have the following characteristics: It should increase the bioavailability of the drug; It should provide for controlled drug delivery; It should transport the drug intact to the site of action while avoiding the non-diseased host tissues; The product should be stable and delivery should be maintained under various physiological variables; A high degree of drug dispersion; The same method should be applicable to a wide range of drugs; It should be easy to administer to the patients; It should be safe and reliable and above all cost-effective (Jain 2008).

1.2 Drug delivery routes

They may be intended for systemic effects or targeted to various organs and diseases. Drugs may be administered directly to the organ affected by disease or given systemically and targeted to the diseased organ. Different routes include:

Gastrointestinal system; oral and rectal, Parenteral: subcutaneous injection, intramuscular injection, intravenous injection, intra-arterial injection, Transmucosal: buccal and through

mucosa lining the rest of gastrointestinal tract, transnasal, pulmonary, transdermal and intra-osseous infusion (Jain, 2008).

1.2.1 Oral drug delivery

The oral route of drug administration has been the one used most for both conventional as well as novel drug delivery because of convenience and widespread acceptability. Major limitations include:

1. Drugs taken orally for systemic effects have variable absorption rates and variable serum concentrations which may be unpredictable. This has led to the development of sustained release and controlled-release systems.
2. The high acid content and ubiquitous digestive enzymes of the digestive tract can degrade some drugs well before they reach the site of absorption into the bloodstream. This is a particular problem for ingested proteins. Therefore, this route has limitations for administration of biotechnology products.
3. Many macromolecules and polar compounds cannot effectively traverse the cells of the epithelial membrane in the small intestines to reach the bloodstream. Their use is limited to local effect in the gastrointestinal tract.
4. Many drugs become insoluble at the low pH levels encountered in the digestive tract. Since only the soluble form of the drug can be absorbed into the bloodstream, the transition of the drug to the insoluble form can significantly reduce bioavailability.
5. The drug may be inactivated in the liver on its way to the systemic circulation. An example of this is the inactivation of glyceryl trinitrate by hepatic monooxygenase enzymes during the first pass metabolism.
6. Some drugs irritate the gastrointestinal tract and this is partially counteracted by coating.

7. Oral route may not be suitable for drugs targeted to specific organs.
8. Despite disadvantages, the oral route remains the preferred route of drug delivery. Several improvements have taken place in the formulation of drugs for oral delivery for improving their action (Jain, 2008).

1.2.2 Enhancing oral absorption

Many medicinal agents are highly lipophilic and poorly soluble because they are designed to optimise specificity and potency (Briones *et al.*, 2008). Yet, a material must be in solution to be transported to the systemic circulation; however it must also be sufficiently lipophilic to partition from the aqueous intestinal contents to the enterocytes lining the small intestine. It might be difficult to incorporate such competing features in a chemical structure. Consequently, absorption might be suboptimal, variable, dose dependent or combinations of these, leading to plasma level variations and unreliable therapeutic response or greater incidence of side effects. Local effects are also possible, consequent to poor absorption. Gastrointestinal side effects during treatment with broad-spectrum antibiotics have been ascribed to unabsorbed antibiotic killing symbiotic bacteria and subsequent overgrowth of resistant flora (Cannon *et al.*, 2005).

Absorption can be influenced by the physico-chemical properties of the drug, the amount administered and by patient physiology (including disease effects). Optimising absorption could involve using a different solid state form of the drug, altering the properties of the existing form, formulation with materials that enhance absorption, exploiting the physiology of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract or capitalising on pre-hepatic metabolic and transport systems (Fahr *et al.*, 2007; Briones *et al.*, 2008). Generally, certain features are used as rule of thumb to indicate whether a molecule is likely to be orally bioavailable (Bioactive). These features are referred to as Lipinski's rule of five. The rule

of five is so called because most of the features start with the number five. Orally active drug has: (Lipinsky *et al.*, 1997)

- Not more than 5 hydrogen bond donors (OH and NH groups)
- Not more than 10 hydrogen bond acceptors (notably N and O)
- A molecular weight under 500
- A Log P under 5

1.3 Bio-pharmaceutics classification systems (BCS)

BCS divides compounds into four classes based on their permeability and solubility (Figure 1). This classification system is useful in predicting effects of efflux and uptake transporters on oral absorption as well as on post-absorption systemic levels following oral and intravenous dosing (Khan, 2001; Lobenberg *et al.*, 2000; Sachan *et al.*, 2009).

Figure 1: Membrane transporter solution according to BCS (Wu and Beret, 2005).

Class 1 (high solubility, high permeability): The high permeability/high solubility of such compounds allows high concentrations in the gut to saturate any transporter, both efflux and absorptive. Class 1 compounds may be substrates for both uptake and efflux transporters *in vitro* in cellular systems, but transporter effects on absorption will not be important clinically (Sachan *et al.*, 2009).

Efflux transporters may have, however measurable effect on the penetration of the compounds through the blood-brain barrier. If the systemic concentration of the compounds is lower, transporters may overcome the effect of the high passive permeability of the compound. These compounds can also be involved in transporter mediated drug-drug interactions.

Class 2 (low solubility, high permeability): These high permeability compounds will pass through the gut membranes and uptake transporters will have no effect on absorption. However, the low solubility will limit the concentration at the enterocytes, thereby preventing saturation of the efflux transporters (Devane *et al.*, 1998; Sachan *et al.*, 2009). Consequently, efflux transporters will affect the extent of oral bioavailability and the rate of absorption of Class 2 compounds.

Class 3 (high solubility, low permeability): For Class 3 compounds, the drug availability will be sufficient in the gut lumen due to good solubility, but an uptake transporter will be necessary to overcome the poor permeability of these compounds. Apical efflux transporters may also be important for the absorption of such compounds when sufficient penetration is achieved via an uptake transporter.

Class 4 (low solubility, low permeability): Due to the low permeability and low solubility of these compounds both uptake and efflux transporters play an important role in the oral bioavailability of Class 4 compounds. The class IV drugs present a major challenge for the

development of drug delivery systems and the route of choice, due to their poor solubility and permeability characteristics. These are often administered by parenteral route with the formulation containing solubility enhancers (Sachan *et al.*, 2009).

1.4 Lipids and its classification

Lipids are organic compounds of plants and animals that are insoluble in water but are soluble in non polar organic solvents e.g. ether, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene etc. (Rama, 2005; Jain *et al.*, 2005). They chemically belong to the class of esters and play an important role biologically. The name lipid comes from the Greek word “*lipos*”, which means fat. Lipids are mainly composed of carbon, hydrogen and oxygen and its general classification shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Flow diagram showing the general classification of lipids (Suneel, 2011)

Lipids can be grouped into different categories based upon their chemical composition as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Classification of the lipophilic excipient based on category (Jaspart *et al.*, 2005)

Category	Description
Fatty alcohol	Cetyl alcohol Stearyl alcohol
Fatty acids	Stearic acid (C ₁₈ fatty acids)
Fatty acid esters of glycerol	Glyceryl monostearate Glyceryl monobehenate Glyceryl behenate Glyceryl palmitostearate Glyceryl ditristearate Glyceryl tripalmitate Glyceryl tristearate
Fatty acids of polyglycerol	Tetraglycerol pentastearate Tetraglycerol monostearate
Hydrogenated fatty acid esters	Hydrogenated hardened castor oil
Polar wax	Complex mixtures containing, e.g., esters of acids and hydroxyacids
Others	Saturated polyglycolised glycerides Beeswax Paraffin wax Cholesterol Phospholipids Microcrystalline wax

1.4.1 Lipid digestion and drug solubilization

The presence of exogenous lipids in the small intestine stimulates secretion of endogenous biliary lipids including the bile salt, phospholipids and cholesterol from the gallbladder. In the presence of raised bile salt concentration, the products of lipid digestion

are subsequently incorporated into a series of colloidal structures including the multi-glandular and unicameral vesicles, mixed micelles and micelles. Together these species significantly expand the solubilization capacity of the small intestine for both lipid digestion products and drugs (Suneel, 2011; Humberstone *et al.*, 1997)

Figure 3: Lipid digestion and drug solubilization in the small intestine

Following the ingestion of a lipid-based dosage form, the formulations initially dispersed in the stomach where the digestion of the exogenous dietary/formulation lipid is initiated by the gastric lipase. Shear in the stomach and on gastric emptying assists in emulsification of the formulation prior to emptying into the duodenum. Within the small intestine, pancreatic lipase together with its co-factor co-lipase completes the breakdown of the dietary glycerides to diglyceride, monoglyceride and fatty acids (represented by different degree of shading on surface of lipid droplet). The presence of exogenous lipids

in the small intestine expands the solubilization capacity of the small intestine for both lipid digestion product and drugs as shown in Figure 3 (Suneel, 2011)

The use of lipid based drug formulations that enhance the bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs have gained much interest, because they utilize the well known food effect of the ingested lipids. Lipid based formulations can reduce slow and incomplete dissolution, facilitate the formation of solubilize phases and if lipophilic, increase the amount of drug transported via the intestinal lymphatic system, thereby increasing absorption from the gastrointestinal tract (Humberstone *et al.*, 1997; Porter *et al.*, 2008).

Lipid-based dosage forms represent a distinct class of drug products that have drawn considerable interest and attention from pharmaceutical scientist. Most of the lipid-based drug delivery systems use lipid vesicles or excipient to solubilize lipophilic drugs that are poorly water-soluble in nature, thereby improving drug absorption in the body. The drug solubility and miscibility in the melted lipid, chemical and physical structure of the lipid material, and their polymorphic state determine the loading capacity of drug in the lipid particles. The amount of drug encapsulated can vary from 1% to 5% for hydrophilic compounds and up to 80% for lipophilic compounds (Sanna *et al.*, 2003).

Lipids are ubiquitously distributed compounds that play fundamental roles in the architecture and functionality of all living cells. Therefore they are most commonly studied as components of food stuff and important energy source in the enteral nutrition. From the stand point of drug delivery, lipids are studied namely as components of various oily liquids and dispersions that are designed to increase solubility and bioavailability of drugs belonging to the class II and IV of the biopharmaceutical drug classification (Chowdary *et al.*, 1998).

With their ability to solubilize hydrophobic drug molecules, lipid-based drug delivery systems have proven to improve drug absorption and dissolution rates in the GIT (Stuchlik *et al.*, 2001; Crauste-Manciet *et al.*, 1998). The reasons for increasing interest in the lipid-based drug delivery systems are many fold and include the following;

- ✦ Improved understanding of the manner in which lipids enhance oral bioavailability and reduce plasma profile variability
- ✦ Better characterization and dipodic excipient
- ✦ Formulation versatility and the choice of different drug delivery systems and
- ✦ Improved ability to address the key issues of technology transfer and manufacture scale-up

In vivo fate of lipid in human body: The processing of lipid-based formulations in the human body is highly complex, and the exact mechanism of drug absorption and its fate association with administered lipid are still not clear. Therefore the focus of this section is to simplify the understanding of the entire process by dividing it into three phases.

(a) **Digestive phase:** Solubilization of drug in the intestinal fluid by formation of colloidal species viz., vesicles, mixed micelles and micelles.

(b) **Absorption phase:** Interference with enterocytes based transport and metabolic processes, thereby potentially changing drug uptake, efflux, disposition and the formation of metabolites within the enterocytes.

(c) **Circulatory uptake:** By selective lymphatic uptake which reduces the first pass drug metabolism as intestinal lymph travels directly to the systemic circulation (Chakra *et al.*, 2009).

These three phases are explained in the following Figure 4.

Figure 4: Various mechanism of enhancement of drug bioavailability in the presence of lipids

1.4.2 Emulsifiers/co-emulsifiers

Emulsifying agent or surfactant may be defined as "a compound that lowers the surface tension and forms a film at the interface of two immiscible liquids making them miscible". The efficiency of an emulsifying agent is related to its chemical structure, solubility, pH and physical properties. There are two types of emulsifying agents on the basis of their effect;

1. Primary agents (true emulsifying agents) can form and stabilize emulsions by themselves.

2. Auxiliary agents (stabilizers) alone do not form fine emulsions but assist the primary emulsifying agents (Snehal, 2010).

Emulsifiers must be non toxic, compatible with minimum amount used, provide adequate stability to the SLMs by covering their surface. Some commonly used emulsifying agents are shown in Table 2

Table 2: Some commonly used emulsifying agents (Jaspart *et al.*, 2005)

Emulsifiers
Poloxamer 188
Ploxoamer 407
Polysorbate 40 (Tween 40)
Polysorbate 80 (Tween 80)
Sorbitane monopalmitate
Sodium dodecyl sulphate
Polyvinyl alcohol
Soya lecithin
Egg phosphatidyl choline

1.5 Novel lipid based drug delivery systems

New chemical entities (NCEs) in modern discovery libraries, development programs and even old drugs have an ever-increasing number of unconventional physical and chemical properties. In particular, up to 70% of discovery compounds and 40% of pipeline candidates are insoluble in water (Amidon *et al.*, 1995). These promising molecules present unique formulation and development challenges and often suffer from poor bioavailability (Amidon *et al.*, 1995). Therefore, conventional formulation systems cannot be employed (Hauss, 2007). Techniques available for scientists to increase the bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs are either increasing their solubility in biological media of choice, or increasing their dissolution kinetics.

The use of advanced lipid-based drug delivery systems (LBDDS) is a strategy to design pharmaceutical dosage forms with improved therapeutic benefits (Elsayed *et al.*,

2009; Piao *et al.*, 2006). The use of lipids in drug delivery is by no means a new phenomenon. “Old” lipid dosage forms such as suppositories, creams or emulsions have been on the market for a long time, and some of them in use since Egyptian times. However, over the last decade, approaches in new designs of lipid carriers have considerably evolved for the delivery of poorly soluble drugs (Benameur, 2007).

LBDDS can be used to deliver various types of drugs from new chemical entities to more recent new developments for proteins and peptides, nucleic acids (DNA, siRNA), cellular site-specific delivery (Rawat *et al.*, 2008; Almeida *et al.*, 2007; Choi *et al.*, 2004). Lipid-based Dosage forms are administered through many routes: oral, parenteral, ocular, intranasal, dermal/transdermal and vaginal (Gershkovich *et al.*, 2008; Pavelic *et al.*, 2005). There have been recent developments in pulmonary drug delivery. In the inhalation field, excipient considered as GRAS (generally recognized as safe) can comprise materials that are endogenous to the lungs and locally present in large quantities, such as phosphatidylcholine (Pilcer *et al.*, 2010). However, oral remains the preferred route because it is non-invasive, less expensive, and is less prone for side effects, such as injection-site reactions. It is also the easiest and the most convenient method of drug delivery for chronic therapies (Benameur, 2006; Pouton *et al.*, 2008).

Efficacy of lipophilic drug is often hindered due to their poor aqueous solubility leading to low absorption after *in vivo* administration. A part of the administered dose is absorbed and reaches the pharmacological site of action and remainder causes toxicity and undesirable side effects due to unwanted bio-distribution. Enhancement in drug efficacy and lowering of drug toxicity could be achieved through encapsulation and delivering the drug in lipid based delivery system (Pate *et al.*, 2008).

1.5.1 Design of lipid-based DDS

Several LBDDS have been developed over the years, most of them for oral delivery. Hauss has given a comprehensive summary of the development, characterization and use of oral lipid based formulations from both physicochemical and biopharmaceutical perspectives (Hauss, 2007). Fricker has provided/described good examples of different types of lipid-based formulations using phospholipids (Fricker *et al.*, 2010).

1.5.2 Liquid lipid-based formulations

1.5.2.1 Microemulsion/nanoemulsion

The pharmaceutical term “emulsion” is most time used to indicate preparations prepared for internal use. Emulsions for external use are always given a different title that its focus may indicate their use, e.g. lotion and cream (Christopher and Dawn, 2008). An emulsion may be defined as a biphasic system consisting of two immiscible liquids, one of which (the dispersed phase) is finely and uniformly dispersed as globules throughout the second phase (the continuous phase). A microemulsion is a thermodynamically stable system composed of at least water, oil and surfactant/co-surfactant producing a transparent and thermodynamically stable system whose droplet size is 10-140 nm (Karasulu, 2008).

Nanoemulsions or miniemulsions or finely dispersed or ultrafine emulsions are part of a broad class of multiphase colloidal dispersions (Russel *et al.*, 1989). Nanoemulsions are dispersions of nanoscale droplets formed by shear-induced rupturing. The present convention for nanoscale materials are materials comprised of structures having length-scales in the range from 1 to 100 nm; below this range lays the angstrom scale, and well above this range lies the micro scale. Applying this convention to metastable emulsions, nanoemulsions are defined to be emulsions having droplet sizes in the ‘nano’ range. Nanoemulsions hold great promise as useful dispersions of deformable nanoscale droplets

that can have flow properties ranging from liquid to highly solid and optical properties ranging from opaque to nearly transparent. The preparation of nanoemulsions requires high pressure homogenization; the emulsifying agent is generally 1 – 3 % of the oil phase (Mason *et al.*, 2006)

Drugs will partition between the aqueous and hydrophobic phases depending on their lipophilicity. Oral, ocular pulmonary, nasal vaginal and intravenous routes are the main routes of administration. Since emulsions are a thermodynamically unstable system, a third agent, the emulsifier is added to stabilize the system (Agarwal and Rajesh, 2007). Emulsifier stabilizes the system by forming a thin film around the globules of dispersed phase (Javed *et al.*, 2008). Either the dispersed phase or the continuous phase may vary in consistency from that of a mobile liquid to semisolid (Alfred, 2005).

1.5.2.2 Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS)

SEDDS and related systems can be binary systems made of oil and surfactant. Their dispersions have a turbid appearance because lipid droplet sizes are between 200 nm to 5 μm . Self-micro-emulsifying DDS (SMEDDS) or Self-nano-emulsifying DDS (SNEDDS) is an isotropic mixture of lipid, surfactant, co- surfactant and sometimes co-solvents and drug substance that can spontaneously form fine oil-in-water micro-emulsions (particle size less than 100 nm) under mild agitation following dilution with an aqueous phase. SMEDDS are distinguished from SEDDS by the much smaller emulsion droplets produced on dilution, resulting in a transparent or translucent solution. SMEDDS generally contain relatively high concentrations of surfactant (typically 40-60 % w/w), and regularly contain hydrophilic co-solvents (e.g. propylene glycol, polyethylene glycols). They are often described as microemulsion pre-concentrates, as the micro-emulsion is formed on dilution in aqueous media (Grove *et al.*, 2004).

The choice between a SEDDS and a SMEDDS often depends of the intrinsic drug properties and its solubility and dissolution profile during in vitro screening with a number of excipient (Kumar *et al.*, 2010; Rao *et al.*, 2008; Stegemann *et al.*, 2009). SMEDDS have demonstrated to have a high solubilisation capacity, and excellent stability. They can substantially provide reproducible and increased oral bioavailability as they enhance the permeation across the intestinal membrane and eliminate food effects (Rane *et al.*, 2009).

1.6 Solid lipid-based formulations

Recently, increasing research has focused on this area. Techniques to obtain diverse solid or semi-solid lipid-based formulations have been described by several authors (Jannin *et al.*, 2008; Canon *et al.*, 2005)

A solid state microemulsion of cyclosporine was prepared by coating a microemulsion with enteric coating material. Solid SEDDS can be used for several dosage forms (dry emulsions, self emulsifying capsules, implants, sustained/controlled release tablets or pellets, beads, microspheres, nanoparticles, suppositories and can provide flexible solutions for oral and parenteral administration (Rao *et al.*, 2008).

1.6.1 Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs),

SLNs are particulate systems with particle diameters ranging 50-1000nm. They are derived from oil-in- water emulsions, by replacing the liquid oil by a solid lipid. They present several advantages: the lipid matrix is generally made from physiologically well-tolerated lipid components, which decreases the toxicity; they combine physical integrity of particle shape and physical protection capacities of sensitive compounds. They have a stability of around three years and can easily be manufactured at industrial scale (Dingler

et al., 2002). SLNs have been reported to increase the bioavailability of several drugs after oral administration, such as piribedil, cyclosporine A and vinpocetin (Fahr *et al.*, 2007).

Solid lipid particulate systems such as SLNs, lipid micro particles and SLMs have been sought as alternative carriers for therapeutic peptides, proteins and antigens. Formulation as SLNs confers improved protein stability, avoids proteolysis, as well as providing sustained release of the incorporated molecules. Well-known peptides such as cyclosporine A, insulin, calcitonin and somatostatin have been incorporated into solid lipid particles and are currently under investigation (Almeida *et al.*, 2007).

1.6 2 Nano-structured lipid carriers (NLC)

A new generation of nano-structured lipid carriers (NLCs) consisting of a lipid matrix with a special nanostructure has been developed (Muller *et al.*, 2000). This nanostructure improves drug loading and firmly incorporates the drug during storage. These NLCs can be produced by high-pressure homogenization and the process can be modified to yield lipid particle dispersions with solid contents from 30–80 % (Radtke *et al.*, 2005).

NLC are the second generation SLN, NLC are composed of binary mixture of solid lipid and a spatially different liquid lipid as the carrier. This consists of a lipid matrix with a special nanostructure and this nanostructure improves drug loading and firmly incorporates the drug during storage. NLC can be administered, e.g., via the oral, ocular, pulmonary and the intravenous route. NLC accommodate the drug because of their highly unordered lipid structures (Radtke *et al.*, 2005).

Types of NLC: It is well known from the study of suppositories that highly ordered crystalline lipid matrices will lead to drug expulsion. Lipid nanoparticles and microparticles made from blends of solid lipids can experience this, especially when nanoparticles are prepared from highly purified lipids, for example, tristearin (Meghana *et al.*, 2012). The formation of highly ordered modifications, particularly during storage, leaves little space for drug molecules, and the expulsion of drugs leads to drug crystals in suspensions and solid dosage forms. To avoid this problem, the particles should have controlled nanostructure that offers enough space to accommodate the drug. Four different approaches can be adopted for an optimized nanostructure of NLC (Meghana *et al.*, 2012; Joshi *et al.*, 2009).

Figure 5: Different types of NLC: I-highly imperfect matrix; II-multiple O/F/W type; III-non-crystalline amorphous NLC (Radtke *et al.*, 2001).

Type I: Solid lipids and liquid lipids (oils) are blended. The differences in the structures of the lipids and special requirements in the crystallization process lead to a highly disordered, imperfect lipid matrix structure offering space for drug molecules and amorphous clusters of drugs (Meghana *et al.*, 2012). In general, drug solubility is higher in liquid lipids than in solid lipids. Based on this, particles are normally produced with a high content of liquid lipids (oils). During the production process, the liquid lipid particles

(nanoemulsions) are cooled from the molten state to room temperature to crystallize and form solid particles.

Type II: The multiple oil/fat/water, drug can be accommodated in the solid, but at increased solubility in the oily parts of the lipid matrix. At high oil concentrations a miscibility gap of the two lipids (solid lipid plus oil) occurs during the cooling phase, leading to phase separation which means precipitation of tiny oily nano-compartments (Meghana *et al.*, 2012).

Type III: Lipids are mixed in a way that prevents them from crystallizing. The lipid matrix is solid, but in an amorphous state (Meghana *et al.*, 2012; Joshi *et al.*, 2009).

1.6.3 Lipid drug conjugate (LDC)

Lipid drug conjugates (LDCs) are at the forefront of the rapidly developing field of nanotechnology with several potential applications in drug delivery and research. Due to their unique size dependent properties, lipid nanoparticles offer possibility to develop new therapeutics. The ability to incorporate drugs into nanocarriers offers a new prototype in drug delivery that could be used for drug targeting. Hence lipid drug conjugates hold great promise for reaching the goal of controlled and site specific drug delivery and hence attracted a wide attention of researchers (Ratna *et al.*, 2013).

A major problem of SLNs is the low capacity to load hydrophilic drugs due to partitioning effects during the production process. Only highly potent low dose hydrophilic drugs may be suitably incorporated in the solid lipid matrix (Morel *et al.*, 1998). In order to overcome this limitation the so called LDC nanoparticles with drug loading capacities up to 33% have been developed (Muller *et al.*, 2002). An insoluble drug - lipid conjugate bulk is first prepared either by salt formation (e.g. with fatty acid) or by covalent linking

(e.g. to esters or ethers). The obtained LDC is then processed with an aqueous surfactant solution (such as tweens) to a nanoparticulate formulation using high pressure homogenisation (HPH). Such matrices may have potential application in brain targeting of hydrophilic drugs in serious protozoa infections (Olbrich *et al.*, 2002).

Lipid drug conjugate nanoparticles generally are spherical in shape and comprised of a lipid drug core stabilized by a surfactant interfacial region. The core lipids can be fatty acids, acylglycerols, waxes and mixtures of the same. Biological membrane lipids such as phospholipids, sphingomyelins, bile salt such as sodium taurocholate, sterols such as cholesterol, and mixtures of the same are utilized as surfactant stabilizers. Polyethylene glycol incorporation can provide steric stabilization and inhibit immune clearance (Mehrnart *et al.*, 2001). Ligands can be conjugated to nanoparticles to promote tissue targeting. The physical properties of LDC's during prolonged storage can be determined by monitoring changes in zeta potential, particle size, drug content, appearance and viscosity as the function of time. External parameters such as temperature and light appear to be of primary importance for long term stability. The zeta potential should be in general remain higher than -60mV for a dispersion to remain physically stable (Quing *et al.*, 2009; Paliwal *et al.*, 2009).

1.6.4 Solid lipid microparticles (SLMs)

Microparticles or microspheres, as they are interchangeably called, are fine spheres usually less than 1000 um in diameter. Microparticles can be prepared by well-established manufacturing processes (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012). An incorporated drug can be distributed homogeneously throughout the polymer matrix (microparticles), or it can be encapsulated into a polymer surrounding to form a drug reservoir (microcapsules) (Lin Y *et al.*, 2000). Solid Lipid Microparticles (SLMs) are defined as solid lipid, approximately spherical

particles ranging in size from 1 to 1000 μm . They are made of polymeric, waxy or other protective materials, that is, biodegradable synthetic polymers and modified natural products such as starches, gums, proteins, fats and waxes. In recent years, biocompatible lipid microparticles have been reported as potential drug carrier systems, and as alternative materials to polymer (Sanna *et al.*, 2003). They can be considered as physiologically compatible, physic-chemically stable and allowing a large scale production at a relatively low production cost than liposomes (Jaspart *et al.*, 2007). These micrometer-sized particles consist of a solid fat core based on naturally occurring lipids and stabilized by surfactant molecules (Dalpiaz *et al.*, 2008)

Figure 6: General structure of SLM (Maanjunath *et al.*, 2005)

SLMs have been proposed as colloidal drug carrier systems for different administration routes such as oral, topical, ophthalmic, subcutaneous, intramuscular injection and particularly for parenteral administration. SLMs combine the advantages of other colloidal carriers, for instance, physiologically acceptable, good tolerability and allow large scale production and like polymeric particles provide controlled drug release from solid lipid matrix and protect the incorporated drug against chemical degradation (Snehal, 2010).

1.6.4.1 Advantages of solid lipid microparticles

SLMs are better carriers than conventional emulsions as they offer better protection of drug against chemical degradation and more prolonged release. As compared to liposomes, SLMs provide better protection to incorporated drug and there is little or no access of water to inner core of lipid particles.

Additional positive features of potential use of solid lipid microparticles as drug carrier systems include

1. Possibility of controlled drug release and drug targeting
2. Protection of incorporated labile drug against chemical degradation
3. There is chemical and physical storage stability (for both drug and carrier system)
4. Use of biodegradable lipids
5. Allow hydrophilic and/or hydrophobic drugs to be incorporate
6. No appreciable drug leakage from particles due to reduced mobility of incorporated drug molecules.
7. Lack of coalescence after reaching room temperature
8. They can be lyophilized, spray dried and also sterilized by autoclaving or gamma radiation
9. Raw materials and production cost are relatively low (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012).

1.6.4.2 Disadvantages of solid lipid microparticles

1. Possibility of particle growth
2. SLMs dispersions have high water content
3. They adjust the release profile of the incorporated drug.
4. Safety profile may be uncertain

5. Drug loading may be limited due to the solubility and miscibility of the drug in the melted lipid, chemical and physical structure of lipid materials, and their polymorphic state (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012)..

1.6.4.3 Methods of formulation of SLMs

Various methods employed for the preparation of solid lipid microparticles are briefly described below;

i. High pressure homogenization

This is a reliable and powerful technique that employs homogenizers to reduce the particle size to micro or nanometer size range depending on the composition and process parameters (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012). Two general approaches of homogenization technique:

a) Hot homogenization

A pre-emulsion of drug loaded lipid melt and hot aqueous emulsifier phase is obtained using a high shear device. The high pressure homogenizer is preheated at temperature above the lipid melting point and the pre-emulsion is put through the homogenizer once or several times. The formulation is then allowed to cool to room temperature (Snehal, 2010).

Figure 7: Schematic representation of the manufacturing method of SLMs suspensions by hot emulsion technique followed by high-shear homogenization and cooling (Jaspart *et al.*, 2007).

b) Cold homogenization

Drug loaded lipid melt is solidified and milled in liquid nitrogen or dry ice with the help of mortar mill. Ground particles are then dispersed into aqueous surfactant solution heated at 5-10 °C below the melting point and subsequently homogenized at room temperature.

ii. Microemulsion technique

This technique involves the addition of drug dispersed lipid melt into hot aqueous surfactant solution under mild stirring to obtain microemulsion which is then dispersed in water at 2 °C - 10 °C under mild mechanical stirring. Addition of a microemulsion to water leads to precipitation of lipid phase forming fine particles (Gasco, 1993).

iii. Solvent emulsification technique

In this technique lipid matrix is dissolved in water immiscible organic solvent (e.g. chloroform, cyclohexane) which is then emulsified in aqueous phase. Upon evaporation of the solvent, the lipid precipitates forming solid microparticles (Sjostron *et al.*, 1992; Siekmann *et al.*, 1996).

iv. Solvent emulsification diffusion technique

In this technique, partially water miscible solvent (e.g. benzyl alcohol, ethyl formate) is mutually saturated with water to ensure initial thermodynamic equilibrium of both liquids. The lipid is then dissolved in water-saturated solvent and subsequently emulsified with solvent-saturated aqueous surfactant solution at elevated temperatures. The solid microparticles precipitate after the addition of excess water due to diffusion of the solvent from emulsion droplet to the continuous phase (Huet *et al.*, 2002; Trotta *et al.*, 2003).

v. Spray drying

Lipids and drugs are dissolved in an organic solvent and the mixture is then spray dried to get solid lipid microparticles (Brasseur *et al.*, 2000; Killeen 2000).

1.7 Vesicular Systems

The vesicular systems are highly ordered assemblies of one or several concentric lipid bilayer formed, when certain amphiphilic building blocks are confronted with water. Vesicles can be formed from a diverse range of amphiphilic building blocks. Biologic origin of these vesicles was first reported in 1965 by Bingham, and was given the name Bingham bodies (Bangham *et al.*, 1965). For the treatment of intracellular infections, conventional chemotherapy is not effective, due to limited permeation of drugs into cells. This can be overcome by the use of vesicular drug delivery systems (Seema *et al.*, 2012). Encapsulation of a drug in vesicular structures can be predicted to prolong the existence of the drug in systemic circulation and perhaps reduce the toxicity if selective uptake can be achieved. Lipid vesicles are one type of many experimental models of bio-membranes which evolved successfully, as vehicles for controlled delivery. For the treatment of intracellular infections, conventional chemotherapy is not effective due to limited permeation of drugs into cells. This can be overcome by the use of vesicular drug delivery systems. The advantages of vesicular drug delivery system include:

1. Prolong the existence of the drug in systemic circulation and perhaps, reduces the toxicity if selective uptake can be achieved due to the delivery of drug directly to the site of infection.
2. Improves the bioavailability especially in the case of poorly soluble drugs.
3. Both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs can be incorporated.

4. Delays elimination of rapidly metabolized drugs and thus function as sustained release systems (Post *et al.*, 1983; Saurabh *et al.*, 2012).

Along with the number of advantages, vesicular systems have some serious disadvantages which restrict their use: Drugs transport passively, which may lead to low drug loading efficiency and drug leakage in preparation, preservation and transport *in vivo* (Breimer *et al.*, 1985). Stability can also act as a barrier and thus limit their use (Saurabh *et al.*, 2012) vesicular systems include liposomes, sphingosome, niosomes, transferosomes, pharmacosomes and virosomes (Seema *et al.*, 2012).

1.7.1 Liposomes

Liposomes are simple microscopic vesicles in which lipid bilayer structures are present with an aqueous volume entirely enclosed by a membrane, composed of lipid molecule. There are a number of components present in liposomes, with phospholipids and cholesterol being the main ingredients. Liposomes are often distinguished according to their number of lamellae and size. They are classified as small unilamellar vesicles (SUVs), large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs) and large multilamellar vesicles (MLVs) or multivesicular vesicles (MVVs). Large liposomes form spontaneously when phospholipids are dispersed in water above their phase transition temperature and the preparation of SUVs starts usually with MLVs, which then are transformed into small vesicles using an appropriate manufacturing technique, e.g. high pressure homogenization.

The methods of preparation have been classified to the three basic modes of dispersions (Biju *et al.*, 2006).

1. Physical dispersion involving hand shaking and non hand-shaking methods.

2. Solvent dispersion involving ethanol injection, ether injection, double emulsion vesicle method, reverse phase evaporation vesicle method, and stable plurilamellar vesicle method.
3. Detergent solubilization.

Liposomes are characterized for their physical attributes i.e. size, shape, and size distribution, surface charge, percent capture, entrapped volume, lamellarity through freeze fracture microscopy and P-NMR, phase behaviour, drug release, quantitative determination of phospholipids and cholesterol analysis. Liposome has been extensively investigated for their potential application in pharmaceutical formulation. They offer a substantial improvement in therapeutic indices of the drug molecules entrapped in them. Due to their high degree of biocompatibility, liposomes have been used as delivery systems for an assortment of molecules. Applications of liposomes are in immunology, dermatology, vaccine adjuvant, eye disorders, brain targeting, infective disease and in tumour therapy. Liposomes as a potential delivery system for the oral administration of insulin have been extensively studied (Patel *et al.*, 1982). Many scientists observed that liposomes have protective effects against proteolytic digestive enzymes like pepsin and pancreatin and they can increase the intestinal uptake of macromolecules and hence are capable of enhancing insulin uptake. Liposomes with a specifically modified design, i.e. long-circulating and especially actively targeting liposomes, stand a better chance in becoming truly tumour-tropic carriers of photo sensitizers, and can hence be used successfully in photodynamic therapy (Seema *et al.*, 2012).

1.7.2 Ethosomes

Ethosomes are novel carrier system used for delivery of drugs having low penetration through the biological membrane mainly skin (Akiladevi and Basak, 2010).

Ethosomes are lipid vesicles containing phospholipids, alcohol (ethanol and isopropyl alcohol) in relatively high concentration and water, which are used mainly for transdermal delivery of drugs. Ethosomes have higher penetration rate through the skin as compared to liposomes hence these can be used widely in place of liposomes. Although, the exact mechanism for better permeation into deeper skin layers from ethosomes is still not clear. The synergistic effects of combination of phospholipids and high concentration of ethanol in vesicular formulations have been suggested to be responsible for deeper distribution and penetration in the skin lipid bilayers. The size range of ethosomes may vary from tens of nanometers to microns (Touitou, 1996; Patel, 2007).

1.7.3 Pharmacosomes

Pharmacosomes bearing unique advantages over liposome and niosome vesicles have come up as potential alternative to conventional vesicles. Pharmacosomes are the colloidal dispersions of drugs covalently bound to lipids and may exist as ultrafine vesicular, micellar or hexagonal aggregates, depending on the chemical structure of the drug-lipid complex (Vaizoglu and Speiser., 1986). Because the system is formed by linking a drug (pharmakon) to a carrier (soma), they are called pharmacosomes.

Pharmacosomes can pass through biomembranes efficiently and possess advantages over the use of other vesicular systems such as transferosome, liposomes, and niosomes. Any drug possessing a free carboxyl group or an active hydrogen atom ($-OH$, NH_2) can be esterified (with or without a spacer group) to the hydroxyl group of a lipid molecule, thus generating an amphiphilic prodrug, which will facilitate membrane, tissue, or cell wall transfer, in the organism. Any drug with a certain cut-off molecular weight may be formulated as pharmacosomes provided it has active functional groups to integrate with the vesicle-forming amphiphilic molecule. Pharmacosomes impart better

biopharmaceutical properties to the drug, resulting in improved bioavailability. Pharmacosomes have been prepared for various non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs, proteins, cardiovascular and antineoplastic drugs. Pharmacosomes are designed to avoid the usual problems associated with the liposomal entrapment of polar drug molecules like low drug incorporation, leakage and poor stability (Seema *et al.*, 2012).

1.7.4 Transferosomes

Liposomal as well as niosomal systems, are not suitable for transdermal delivery, because of their poor skin permeability, breaking of vesicles, leakage of drug, aggregation, and fusion of vesicles (Cevc *et al.*, 1997). To overcome these problems, a new type of carrier system called "transferosome", has recently been introduced, which is capable of transdermal delivery of low as well as high molecular weight drugs (Schatzlein *et al.*, 1995). Transferosomes are specially optimized, ultradeformable (ultraflexible) lipid supramolecular aggregates, which are able to penetrate the mammalian skin intact. Each transferosome consists of at least one inner aqueous compartment, which is surrounded by a lipid bilayer with specially tailored properties, due to the incorporation of "edge activators" into the vesicular membrane. Due to their deformability, transferosomes are good candidates for the non-invasive delivery of small, medium, and large sized drugs. Transferosomes are vesicles composed by phospholipids as the main ingredient (soya phosphatidylcholine, egg phosphatidylcholine, dipalmityl phosphatidylcholine, etc), 10-25% surfactants for providing flexibility (sodium cholate, tween 80, span-80), 3-10% alcohol as a solvent (ethanol, methanol) and hydrating medium consisting of saline phosphate buffer (pH 6.5-7) (Seema *et al.*, 2012).

1.8 Review of drug and excipient

1.8.1 Rifampicin

A semi synthetic antibiotic produced from *Streptomyces mediterranei*. It has a broad antibacterial spectrum, including activity against several forms of Mycobacterium. In susceptible organisms it inhibits DNA-dependent RNA polymerase activity by forming a stable complex with the enzyme. It thus suppresses the initiation of RNA synthesis. Rifampicin is bactericidal, and acts on both intracellular and extracellular organisms (Gilman et al., 2006). RMP is a bactericidal antibiotic drug of the rifamycin group. It is a semi-synthetic compound derived from *Amycolatopsis rifamycinica* (formerly known as *Amycolatopsis mediterranei* and *Streptomyces mediterranei*). Rifampicin may be abbreviated R, RMP, RA, RF, or RIF (USA). Rifampicin is an intensely red solid, and the small fraction which reaches body fluids is known for imparting a harmless red-orange colour to the urine (and to a lesser extent, also sweat and tears) of users, for a few hours after a dose. Maximal concentrations in the blood are decreased by about a third when the antibiotic is taken with food.

Structure:

Systematic (IUPAC) name

(7S,9E,11S,12R,13S,14R,15R,16R,17S,18S,19E,21Z)-2,15,17,27,29-pentahydroxy-11-methoxy-3,7,12,14,16,18,22-heptamethyl-26-[(E)-[(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)imino]methyl]-6,23-dioxo-8,30-dioxa-24-azatetracyclo[23.3.1.1,.0,]triaconta-1(28),2,4,9,19,21,25(29),26-octaen-13-yl acetate

Physical properties

Appearance: Orange-brown to red-brown powder.

Molecular formula: C₄₃H₅₈N₄O₁₂

Molecular weight: 823.0 g/mol

pKa (in water): 1.7 (4-hydroxyl group), 7.9 (4-piperazine nitrogen); in methylcellulose-water (4:1): 3.6 (4-hydroxyl group), 6.7 (3-piperazine nitrogen).

Optical rotation: $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +10.6^\circ$ (Gallo *et al.*, 1976).

Melting point: 183-188 °C (361 - 370 °F)

Bioavailability: 90 to 95 %

Metabolism: Hepatic and intestinal wall

Half-life: 1.5 to 5 hours

Excretion: 15 to 30 % renal, 60 % faecal

Stability/storage: Rifampicin (RMP) should be stable for at least two years when stored desiccated at -20 °C and protected from light (Sigma quality control data). RMP is stable as a solid at temperatures up to 70 °C (Gallo *et al.*, 1976).

Solubility/solution stability: RMP is soluble in dimethylsulfoxide (100 mg/ml), dimethylformamide, methanol (16 mg/ml, 25 °C), chloroform (349 mg/ml, 25 °C), ethyl acetate (108 mg/ml, 25 °C), and acetone (14 mg/ml, 25 °C) (Moffat *et al.*, 1986; Gallo *et al.*, 1976; Karlson *et al.*, 1969) . RMP is slightly soluble in water at 25 °C: 2.5 mg/ml, pH 7.3; 1.3 mg/ml, pH 4.3; and in 95 % ethanol (10 mg/ml) (Gallo *et al.*, 1976). RMP is soluble at 37 °C: in 0.1 N HCl, 200 mg/ml and in phosphate buffer pH 7.4, 9.9 mg/ml (Gallo *et al.*, 1976).

A 1% suspension in water has a pH of 4.5 - 6.5 (Gallo *et al.*, 1976). Solution stability of RMP in DMSO is 10 mg/ml, about 8 months at 15 °C (Karlson *et al.*, 1969) water-ethanol (8:2), 1 mg/ml, 8 weeks at 4 °C or 20 °C (Gallo *et al.*, 1976; Merck index). In mildly basic aqueous solutions (pH 8.2, 20-22 °C) in the presence of air, RMP is converted to rifampicin quinone. Addition of sodium ascorbate can prevent its oxidation. Under basic conditions RMP undergoes deacetylation at 22 °C forming the 25-desacetylrifampicin (most of antibacterial activity is maintained) (Gallo *et al.*, 1976). RMP decomposes rapidly in acidic or alkaline conditions at 25 °C but slowly in neutral conditions, i.e. at 200 µg/ml, at pH 2.3 RMP is hydrolyzed to 3-formylrifampicin (Gallo *et al.*, 1976; Maggi *et al.* 1966). It is best to prepare aqueous solutions with oxygen-free solvent and at neutral pH.

Antibacterial activity: Rifampicin inhibits the growth of most gram-positive bacteria as well as many gram-negative microorganisms such as *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas*, indole-positive and indole-negative *Proteus*, and *Klebsiella*. Rifampicin is very active

against *Staphylococcus aureus* and coagulase-negative staphylococci. The drug also is highly active against *Neisseria meningitidis* and *Haemophilus influenzae*; minimal inhibitory concentrations range from 0.1 to 0.8 mg/ml. Rifampicin inhibits the growth of *Legionella* species in cell culture and in animal models (Gilman *et al.*, 2006).

Rifampicin in concentrations of 0.005 to 0.2 mg/ml inhibits the growth of *M. tuberculosis* in vitro. Among non-tuberculous mycobacteria, *M. kansasii* is inhibited by 0.25 to 1 mg/ml. The majority of strains of *Mycobacterium scrofulaceum*, *Mycobacterium intracellulare*, and *M. avium* are suppressed by concentrations of 4 mg/ml, but certain strains may be resistant to 16 mg/ml. *Mycobacterium fortuitum* is highly resistant to the drug. Rifampicin increases the in vitro activity of streptomycin and isoniazid, but not that of ethambutol, against *M. Tuberculosis* (Gilman *et al.*, 2006).

Mechanism of action: Rifampicin inhibits DNA-dependent RNA polymerase of mycobacteria and other microorganisms by forming a stable drug-enzyme complex, leading to suppression of initiation of chain formation (but not chain elongation) in RNA synthesis. More specifically, the β -subunit of this complex enzyme is the site of action of the drug, although rifampicin binds only to the holoenzyme. Nuclear RNA polymerases from a variety of eukaryotic cells do not bind rifampicin, and RNA synthesis is correspondingly unaffected in eukaryotic cells. High concentrations of rifampicin antibiotics can inhibit RNA synthesis in mammalian mitochondria, viral DNA-dependent RNA polymerases, and reverse transcriptases. Rifampicin is bactericidal for both intracellular and extracellular microorganisms (Gilman *et al.*, 2006).

Absorption, distribution, and excretion: The oral administration of rifampicin produces peak concentrations in plasma in 2 to 4 hours; after ingestion of 600 mg, this value is about 7 mg/ml, but there is considerable variability. Aminosalicylic acid may delay the

absorption of rifampicin and cause a failure to reach adequate plasma concentrations. If aminosalicylate and rifampicin are used concurrently, they should be given separately at an interval of 8 to 12 hours.

Following absorption from the gastrointestinal tract, rifampicin is eliminated rapidly in the bile, and an enterohepatic circulation ensues. During this time, the drug is progressively deacetylated, such that after 6 hours, nearly the entire antibiotic in the bile is in the deacetylated form, which retains essentially full antibacterial activity. Intestinal reabsorption is reduced by deacetylation (as well as by food), and thus metabolism facilitates elimination of the drug. The half-life of rifampicin varies from 1.5 to 5 hours and is increased by hepatic dysfunction; the half-life may be decreased in patients receiving isoniazid concurrently who are slow inactivators of isoniazid. The half-life of rifampicin is progressively shortened by about 40 % during the first 14 days of treatment, owing to induction of hepatic microsomal enzymes that accelerate rifampicin deacetylation. Up to 30 % of a dose of the drug is excreted in the urine and 60 % to 65 % in the faeces; less than half of this may be unaltered antibiotic. Adjustment of dosage is not necessary in patients with impaired renal function (Gilman *et al.*, 2006).

Rifampicin is distributed throughout the body and is present in effective concentrations in many organs and body fluids, including the CSF. This is perhaps best exemplified by the fact that the drug may impart an orange-red colour to the urine, faeces, saliva, sputum, tears, and sweat; patients should be so notified (Furesz, 1970; Farr, 2000).

Therapeutic uses: Rifampicin for oral administration is available alone and as a fixed-dose combination with isoniazid (150 mg of isoniazid, 300 mg of rifampicin; Rifamate®) or with isoniazid and pyrazinamide (50 mg of isoniazid, 120 mg of rifampicin, and 300 mg pyrazinamide; Rifater®). A parenteral form of rifampicin is available for use when the

drug cannot be taken by mouth. Rifampicin and isoniazid are the most effective drugs available for the treatment of tuberculosis.

The dose of rifampicin for treatment of tuberculosis in adults is 600 mg, given once daily, either 1 hour before or 2 hours after a meal. Children should receive 10 mg/kg given in the same way. Doses of 15 mg/kg or higher are associated with increased hepatotoxicity in children (Centers for Disease Control, 1980). Rifampicin, like isoniazid, should never be used alone for the treatment of tuberculosis because of the rapidity with which resistance may develop. Despite the long list of untoward effects from rifampicin, their incidence is low, and treatment seldom has to be interrupted.

Rifampicin also is indicated for the prophylaxis of meningococcal disease and *H. influenza* meningitis. To prevent meningococcal disease, adults may be treated with 600 mg twice daily for 2 days or 600 mg once daily for 4 days; children should receive 10 to 15 mg/kg, to a maximum of 600 mg.

Bacterial resistance: Microorganisms, including mycobacteria, may develop resistance to rifampicin rapidly in vitro as a one-step process, and one of every 10⁷ to 10⁸ tubercle bacilli is resistant to the drug. Microbial resistance to rifampicin is due to an alteration of the target of this drug, DNA-dependent RNA polymerase, with resistance in most cases being due to mutations between codons 507 and 533 of the polymerase *rpoB* gene (Blanchard, 1996); the mutations reduce binding of the drug to the polymerase. As a consequence, the antibiotic must not be used alone in the chemotherapy of tuberculosis. When rifampicin has been used to eradicate the meningococcal carrier state, failures have been due to the appearance of drug-resistant bacteria after treatment for as few as 2 days. Certain rifampicin-resistant bacteria mutants have decreased virulence. Tuberculosis caused by rifampicin-resistant mycobacteria has been described in patients who had not

received prior chemotherapy, but this is very rare, usually less than 1% (Cauthen *et al.*, 1988).

Untoward effects: Rifampicin generally is well tolerated. When given in usual doses, fewer than 4 % of patients with tuberculosis have significant adverse reactions; the most common are rash (0.8 %), fever (0.5 %), and nausea and vomiting (1.5 %) (Grosset and Leventis, 1983). Rarely, hepatitis and deaths due to liver failure have been observed in patients who received other hepatotoxic agents in addition to rifampicin, or who had pre-existing liver disease. Hepatitis from rifampicin rarely occurs in patients with normal hepatic function; likewise, the combination of isoniazid and rifampicin appears generally safe in such patients (Gangadharam, 1986). However, chronic liver disease, alcoholism, and old age appear to increase the incidence of severe hepatic problems when rifampicin is given alone or concurrently with isoniazid.

Rifampicin should not be administered on an intermittent schedule (less than twice weekly) and/or in daily doses of 1.2 g or greater because this is associated with frequent side effects. A flulike syndrome with fever, chills, and myalgias develops in 20 % of patients so treated. The syndrome also may include eosinophilia, interstitial nephritis, acute tubular necrosis, thrombocytopenia, hemolytic anemia, and shock.

Because rifampicin potently induces CYP1A2, 2C9, 2C19, and 3A4, its administration results in a decreased half-life for a number of compounds, including HIV protease and non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors, digitoxin, digoxin, quinidine, disopyramide, mexiletine, tocainide, ketoconazole, propranolol, metoprolol, clofibrate, verapamil, methadone, cyclosporine, corticosteroids, oral anticoagulants, theophylline, barbiturates, oral contraceptives, halothane, fluconazole, and the sulfonylureas (Farr, 2000).

Rifabutin has less effect on the metabolism of many of the HIV protease inhibitors. The significant interaction between rifampicin and oral anticoagulants of the coumarin type leads to a decrease in efficacy of these agents. This effect appears about 5 to 8 days after rifampicin administration is started and persists for 5 to 7 days after it is stopped. The ability of rifampicin to enhance the catabolism of a variety of steroids leads to the decreased effectiveness of oral contraceptives, and can induce adrenal insufficiency in patients with marginal adrenocortical reserve. The increased metabolism of methadone and other narcotics has led to reports of precipitation of withdrawal syndromes and inadequate pain control unless the dose is increased. Rifampicin may reduce biliary excretion of contrast media used for visualization of the gallbladder (Baciewicz *et al.*, 1987).

Gastrointestinal disturbances produced by rifampicin (epigastric distress, nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps, diarrhea) have occasionally required discontinuation of the drug. Various symptoms related to the nervous system also have been noted, including fatigue, drowsiness, headache, dizziness, ataxia, confusion, inability to concentrate, generalized numbness, pain in the extremities, and muscular weakness. Hypersensitivity reactions include fever, pruritus, urticaria, various types of skin eruptions, eosinophilia, and soreness of the mouth and tongue. Hemolysis, hemoglobinuria, hematuria, renal insufficiency, and acute renal failure have been observed rarely; these also are thought to be hypersensitivity reactions. Thrombocytopenia, transient leukopenia, and anemia have occurred during therapy. Since the potential teratogenicity of rifampicin is unknown and the drug is known to cross the placenta, it is best to avoid the use of this agent during pregnancy.

Graber and associates (1973) noted immunoglobulin light-chain proteinuria (kappa, lambda, or both) in about 85 % of patients with tuberculosis treated with rifampicin. None

of the patients had symptoms or electrophoretic patterns compatible with myeloma. However, renal failure has been associated with light-chain proteinuria (Warrington *et al.*, 1977).

Rifampicin is effective for chemoprophylaxis of meningococcal disease and meningitis due to *H. influenzae* in household contacts of patients with such infections. Combined with a b-lactam antibiotic or vancomycin, rifampicin may be useful for therapy in selected cases of staphylococcal endocarditis (on both natural and prosthetic valves) or osteomyelitis, especially those caused by staphylococci "tolerant" to penicillin. Rifampicin may be indicated for treatment of infections in patients with inadequate leukocytic bactericidal activity and for eradication of the staphylococcal nasal carrier state in patients with chronic furunculosis (Gilman *et al.*, 2006).

Summary of adverse reactions: Nausea, vomiting, epigastric distress, heartburn, fatigue, dizziness, rash, hematologic changes, and renal insufficiency may be seen with administration of rifampicin. Rifampicin may also cause a reddish-orange discoloration of body fluids, including urine, tears, saliva, sweat, and sputum.

Contraindications, precautions, and interactions: Rifampicin is contraindicated in patients with a history of hypersensitivity to the drug. The drug is used with caution during lactation, in patients with hepatic and renal impairment, and during pregnancy. Serum concentrations of digoxin may be decreased by rifampicin. Isoniazid and rifampicin administered concurrently may result in a higher risk of hepatotoxicity than when either drug is used alone. The use of rifampicin with the oral anticoagulants or oral hypoglycemics may decrease the effects of the anticoagulant or hypoglycemic drug. There is a decrease in the effect of the oral contraceptives, chloramphenicol, phenytoin, and

verapamil when these agents are administered concurrently with rifampicin (Gilman *et al.*, 2006).

1.8.2 *Irvingia wombolu*

Taxonomy

Current name: *Irvingia wombolu*

Authority: Vermoesen

Family: Irvingiaceae

Synonym(s): *Irvingia gabonensis*

Common names: (English): bitter bush mango (Harris, 1993).

Botanic description: *Irvingia wombolu* is a tree to 25-30 m tall, buttressed up to 2 m. The stem is often leaning and glabrous. The first branches are usually at a height of 7-10 m. Foliage regular, not as dense as in the *Irvingia gabonensis*. Leaves simple, alternate, entire, obovate, and less leathery, length 10.5 - 14 cm, width 4 - 8.5 cm, leaf apex rounded, often with a barely distinct blunt acumen, base obtuse to acute, occasionally very shortly cuneate. Leaf stipules leave an annular scar around the stem when they fall off and fruits with green skin which may turn yellow on ripening. Flesh of fruit yellow, soft, juicy and fibrous, extremely bitter and inedible. When the flesh rots away the fruit the shell may have some curly fibres attached to it. The shell wall is less than 7 mm thick and is easy to break open using a wooden club or a stone. This tree closely resembles *Irvingia gabonensis*, genetic data indicates significant differences between the two, supporting (Harris, 1996) conclusion that the taxa are distinct genetic entities. The genus name commemorates E.G. Irving, 1816-1855, a Scottish botanist.

Ecology and distribution

History of cultivation: *I. wombolu* is well known and has been utilized for a long time in Nigeria and parts of Cameroon. Reports of cultivation of this species are given. So far no reliable reports of wild *I. wombolu* in forests are recorded. The bitter bush mango fetches high prices in cross-border trade contributing significantly to the economy of the central and West African region as a whole (Lodoen, 1998; Whitmore, 1983).

Natural habitat: The bitter bush mango shows a wider rainfall regime tolerance than the other *Irvingia* species. It occurs in dry land forest in areas with more than 1500 mm rainfall across the southern half of the Central African Republic from Cameroon in the west to Sudan in the east. In some localities it is common in swamps and seasonally flooded forest than in adjacent dry land forest (Harris, 1996; Lodoen, 1998).

Geographic distribution

Native : Angola, Cameroon, Congo, Cote d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ghana, Guinea, Liberia, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Uganda.

Biophysical limits: Mean annual rainfall-: 1500 - 2500 mm Soil type; prefers dry or seasonally flooded soils.

Reproductive biology: *I. wombolu* flowers at the end of the rainy season (October-November), but depending on conditions, flowering time overlaps in some years and regions. Fruiting is at the end of the dry season (February-April). The flowers, appearing 6-10 years after planting, are insect pollinated. There is no evidence of hybridization with the closely related *I. gabonensis*. There is a decrease in genetic similarity over distance. Results from RAPD analysis indicate marked (similarity estimates) differences between Cameroonian and Nigerian material. Southern Nigeria and southern Cameroon material

harbour rare alleles and significantly high levels of genetic diversity. Fruits passed out in elephant dung show successful germination. Red forest pigs and squirrels open the pyrenes eating the seeds only (Lowe et al., (unpubl); Lodoen, 1998).

Propagation and management

Tree management: The members of the genus *Irvingia* are fire tender.

Germ plasm management: Germination is epigeous and phanerocotylar, beginning at about one month and occurring faster under the mother tree. The seeds of *I. wombolu* are recalcitrant and should be sown fresh.

Functional uses

Food: The seeds are collected and their cotyledons grilled or dried in the sun, pounded then used in preparation of a local dish 'gumbo'. The mesocarp is inedible. *I. wombolu* seeds give a more mucilaginous texture to food; this attribute makes the seeds command a higher market price. Overcooking causes the loss of sliminess. The sauce keeps for several days without refrigeration. The dried kernel can be stored for up to a year, as can the paste if it is thoroughly dried in the sun. Apiculture: Insects visit the flowers for pollen.

Medicine: The fresh bark of the tree is considered to be a powerful antibiotic against scabies, a cure for diarrhoea when mixed with palm oil and a toothache remedy (Harris, 1994).

Services (shade or shelter): The bitter bush mango provides adequate shade.

Intercropping: *I. wombolu* has high agro-forestry potential. In its native range it is found cultivated with other crops in farm systems (Harris, 1994).

1.8.3 Polysorbate 80 (Rowe *et al.*, 2006)

Structure

Synonyms: Tween 80; Polyoxyethylene 20 oleate (Z)-sorbitan mono-9-octadecenoate poly (oxy-(1, 2-ethanedyl) derivative

Chemical name: Polyoxyethylene 20-sorbitan monooleate

Empirical formula and molecular weight: C₆₄H₁₂₄O₂₆

Typical properties

HLB value: 15

Viscosity: 425 mpaS

Solubility: Soluble in ethanol and water, insoluble in mineral oil and vegetable.

Functional category: Emulsifying agent, nonionic surfactant, solubilizing agent, wetting agent, dispersing agent and suspending agent.

Stability and storage: Polysorbates are stable to electrolytes, weak acids and bases. Gradual saponification occurs with strong acids and bases. Polysorbates should be stored in well--closed container, protected from light in cool, dry place.

1.8.4 Phospholipon® 90 H

Phosphatidylcholine, hydrogenated. Phospholipon 90H is a completely hydrogenated soy lecithin.

Fatty acid composition: approx. 85 % stearic acid, approx. 15 % palmitic acid.

Applications: Preparation of liposomes and emulsions for pharmaceuticals and cosmetics, and skin protectant.

Characteristics: Phase transition temperature in hydrated form: approx. 55 °C

Properties: white, crystalline powder

Solubility: clear solution (10 % in CHCl₃ /Methanol = 2/1 v/v)

Iodine value: max. 1

Fatty acids: Sum stearic acid and palmitic acid: min. 98 %

Sum unsaturated fatty acids (oleic, linoleic, linolenic acids): max. 2 %

Moisture (Karl Fisher): max. 2 %

Residual solvents: Ethanol: max. 0.5 %

Acetone: max. 50 ppm

Ethylmethylketone: max. 50 ppm (Drug Master File N° 16614 (USA))

1.8.5 Sorbitol

Sorbitol, also known as glucitol, is a sugar alcohol, which the human body metabolizes slowly. It can be obtained by reduction of glucose, changing the aldehyde group to a hydroxyl group. Most sorbitol is made from corn syrup, but it is also found in apples, pears, peaches, and prunes (Teo *et al.*, 2006). It is synthesized by sorbitol-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, and converted to fructose by succinate dehydrogenase and sorbitol dehydrogenase. Succinate dehydrogenase is an enzyme complex that participates in the citric acid cycle (Teo *et al.*, 2006).

Synonyms: d-glucitol, d-sorbitol, sorbit, sorbol, ins no. 420(i)

Chemical names: D-Sorbitol

Chemical formula: C₆H₁₄O₆

Structural formula:

Formula weight: 182.17

Description: White hygroscopic powder, crystalline powder, flakes or granules

Functional uses: Sweetener, humectant, sequestrant, texturizer, stabilizer, bulking agent

Characteristics

Solubility: Very soluble in water, slightly soluble in ethanol

Melting range: 88 - 102°, (JECFA, 1996)

1.8.6 Sorbic acid

Chemical names: Sorbic acid, 2, 4-hexadienoic acid, 2-propenylacrylic acid

Chemical formula: C₆H₈O₂

Structural formula:

Formula weight: 112.12

Description: Colourless needles or white free flowing powder, having a slight characteristic odour

Functional uses: Antimicrobial preservative, fungistatic agent

Characteristics

Solubility: Slightly soluble in water, soluble in ethanol.

Melting range: Between 132 and 135° (JECFA, 1976)

1.9 Objectives of study

The present work is planned with the following objectives:

1. To prepare solid-lipid microparticles (SLMs) systems consisting of model drug (rifampicin) and carriers (phospholipon 90H and *Irvingia wombolu* fat) by employing hot melt homogenisation method.
2. To determine the effects of some process variables on the properties of the formulated SLMs.
3. To determine the effect of lyophilization on particle size.
4. To study *in vitro* and *in vivo* drug release profiles.

Aim

The aim of this study is to investigate the possibility of improving the solubility and thus eliminate the variability in the bioavailability of rifampicin by formulating it as solid lipid microparticles (SLMs).

CHAPTER 2

Materials and methods

2.1 Materials and equipment

The following materials were used as procured from their suppliers without further purification: hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide, potassium dihydrogen phosphate and Tween® 80, (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), sorbitol (Wharfedale Laboratories, Otley, West Yorkshire LS211LH, England), rifampicin (a kind gift from Mobson Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd, Isolo, Lagos State), Phospholipon® 90H (Phospholipid GmbH, Koln, Germany), *Irvingia wombolu* Fat (Obtained from a batch processed by Dr I.V. Onyishi at Dept. of Pharmaceutical Technology and industrial Pharmacy Lab. UNN) and distilled water (Energy centre, University of Nigeria Nsukka), Broth culture of the test organisms (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*), Sterile Petri dish, Pasteur pipette and cork borer, Two sterile pipettes (5 ml and 1 ml capacity), Molten nutrient agar (15 ml at 45 °C). All other reagents and solvents are of analytical grade and used as supplied. Equipments include the following:

- a) Magnetic heater and stirrer (SR1 UM 52188, Remi Equipment, Mumbai, India)
- b) Ultra turrax homogenizer (T25 Basic Digital, Ika, Staufen, Germany)
- c) Ultra-violet spectrophotometer (Spectrum Lab, 752S, Breda, Netherland)
- d) pH meter (pH ep® Hanna instrument, Padova, Italy)
- e) Analytical balance (Adventurer, Ohaus, China)
- f) Freeze-dryer (Amsco/Finn – Aqua® Lyovac GTZ, Hürth, Germany)
- g) Hund® binocular microscope (Helmut Hund GmbH, Weltzlar, Germany) attached with a Motic image analyser (Moticam, Xiamen, China) at a magnification of X 400).

- h) Digital scanning calorimetry (DSC) (Netzsch DSC 204 F1, Geratebau, GmbH, Selb, Germany)
- i) The polycarbonate dialysis membrane (MWCO 6000–8000, Spectrum Labs, Breda, the Netherlands)
- j) Filter paper (Whatman No. 1)
- k) Electronic balance (Adventurer AR3130, Ohaus, China; YP-1002N, RS232C, China)
- l) Thermostatic water bath (Electric Thermostat Water tank For Three Usages, H-W21-Cr-42 II, China)

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Preparation of lipid matrix

About two batches of lipid matrix were prepared with different ratio range 1:2 and 1:3 of the *Irvingia wombolu* fat and Phospholipon 90H. The amount of lipid matrix required to prepare 2 different batches of the solid lipid microparticles was calculated and the actual weight of both the *Irvingia wombolu* fat and Phospholipon[®] 90H (P90H) were also calculated. In the first batch for the ratio 1:2, 16.7 g of P90H and 33.3 g *Irvingia wombolu* fat were weighed out respectively and melted together. P90H melted at a higher temperature compared to *Irvingia wombolu*. The second batch for ratio 1:3, 12.5 g of P90H and 37.5 g of *Irvingia wombolu* fat were weighed respectively and melted together. After melting for the different batches, the lipid matrix was stirred until a homogenous mix of the lipid was formed. (Total weight of lipid matrix = 50.0 g)

2.2.2 Preparation of SLMs

The Rifampicin-loaded SLMs were prepared using the melt homogenization technique (Jaspart *et al.*, 2007). The microparticles were prepared using 1:1 and 1:3 (w/w)

lipid matrices by hot homogenization using ultra-turrax homogenizer (T25 Basic Digital, Ika, Staufen, Germany). In each case, 5 g of the lipid matrix (LM) was melted at 70 °C and an appropriate amount of rifampicin was incorporated into the lipidic melt. The lyoprotectant (sorbitol) was dissolved in hot distilled water at the same temperature with the lipidic melt together with surfactant (Tween 80). The hot aqueous phase was poured into the lipidic melt and immediately subjected to high shear homogenization with ultra-turrax at 10,000 rpm for 5 mins. An o/w emulsion was finally obtained by phase inversion. About 50 ml of SLMs obtained after cooling at room temperature were lyophilized using freeze-dryer (Amsco/Finn – Aqua® Lyovac GTZ, Hürth, Germany) in order to obtain solidified water-free microparticles (Jaspart *et al.*, 2007). SLMs containing no drug (unloaded SLMs), which served as negative control were also formulated.

Table 3: Formula for the preparation of SLM

Batch	LM ratio	Tween 80 (% w/w)	LM (% w/w)	Sorbitol (% w/w)	Sorbic acid (% w/w)	Drug (rifampicin) (% w/w)	Distilled water (% w/w)
P1	1:2	2.0	5	4	0.05	1	100
P2	1:2	2.0	5	4	0.05	2	100
P3	1:2	2.0	5	4	0.05	2.5	100
P4	1:2	2.0	5	4	0.05	-	100
Q1	1:3	2.0	5	4	0.05	1	100
Q2	1:3	2.0	5	4	0.05	2	100
Q3	1:3	2.0	5	4	0.05	2.5	100
Q4	1:3	2.0	5	4	0.05	-	100

LM (Lipid Matrix); Phospholipon® 90H (P90H): *Irvingia wombolu* (*Irw*) fat.

2.2.3 Preparation of calibration curve

A standard curve for Rifampicin was prepared in the concentration range of 0.02-0.10 mg/ml using the absorption maxima. For the preparation of the calibration, stock solution was prepared by dissolving 0.512 g of accurately weighed rifampicin in 100 ml of

methanol, 100 fold serial dilutions was obtained separately by diluting with fluids (SIF, pH 6.8), (phosphate buffer pH 7.4). From this, 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6 and 2.0 ml were withdrawn using a pipette into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to 10 ml with the buffers to get concentrations 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, and 0.10 mg of rifampicin respectively. The optical density values (absorbance) of the resulting solutions were measured at 475 nm using UV/Visible spectrophotometer (Spectrum Lab, 752S, Breda, Netherland). The concentrations versus optical density (absorbance) values were plotted.

2.2.4 Preparation of calibration curve in Plasma

A standard curve for rifampicin was prepared in plasma in the concentration range of 2 - 10 µg/ml. For the preparation of the calibration, stock solution was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of accurately weighed rifampicin in 10 ml of plasma solution mixed with 10 % methanol in distilled water and diluted 10 times to get a stock of 1 mg/ml, 100 fold serial dilutions was obtained from the stock by diluting with 10 % methanol in distilled water (This resultant solution was scanned to obtain the maximum wavelength of absorption of RMP in plasma which was 473 nm). From this, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 ml were withdrawn using a pipette into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to mark with the 10 % methanol in distilled water to get 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 µg concentrations of rifampicin respectively. The optical density values (absorbance) of the resulting solutions were measured at 473 nm obtained during scanning using UV/Visible spectrophotometer (Spectrum Lab, 752S, Breda, Netherland). The concentrations versus optical density (absorbance) values were plotted.

2.2.5 Preparation of simulated intestinal fluid (SIF)

This was done by dissolving 6.8 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 250 ml of distilled water. The resulting solution was made up to 1000 ml with distilled water. The

pH of the solution was checked and adjusted to 6.8 using 0.2 N NaOH (Uronnachi *et al.*, 2013).

2.2.6 Preparation of phosphate buffer, pH 7.4

About 50 ml of 0.2 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate was transferred to a 200 ml volumetric flask. After addition of 39.1 ml of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide, water was added to the volume and mixed thoroughly (Suneel, 2011).

2.2.7 Preparation of simulated gastric fluid (SGF)

A 1.0 g quantity of NaCl was dissolved in 500 ml of distilled water and 7 ml of conc. HCl was added to it. The resulting solution was made up to 1000 ml with distilled water. The pH of the medium was checked and adjusted to 1.2 with a 2.0 N HCl (Uronnachi *et al.*, 2013).

2.3 Characterization of the SLMs

2.3.1 Determination of particle size and morphology

The bottles containing the different batches (1:2 and 1:3) of the formulations were shaken vigorously and were syringed out using 5 ml syringe. Two drops of the different formulations were dispersed on a clean slide using organic solvent in which it is soluble in and was examined under a Hund binocular microscope (Helmut Hund GmbH, Weltzlar, Germany) attached with a Motic image analyser (Moticam, Xiamen, China) at a magnification of $\times 400$ (Nnamani *et al.*, 2010).

For the lyophilized microparticles, 200 mg of the SLMs from each batch was placed on a microscope slide and was dispersed in small amount of water. The slide was covered with a cover slip and imaged under a Hund binocular microscope (Helmut Hund

GmbH, Wetzlar, Germany) attached with a Motic image analyser (Moticam, Xiamen, China) at a magnification of $\times 400$ (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

2.3.2 Percentage yield of microparticles

After lyophilization (50 ml lyophilized), the water-free SLMs from all the batches were weighed. The yield of SLMs (% w/w) was calculated according to the following formula (Attama *et al.*, 2009).

$$\text{Percentage Yield (\%)} = \frac{W1}{W2+W3} \times 100 \quad \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where W1 is weight of SLMs formulated (g), W2 the weight of drug added (g) and W3 the weight of lipid, phospholipon® 90H and *Irvingia wombolu* fat.

2.3.3 Time dependent pH stability studies

The pH of the different batches of the formulation were determined after 24 hours, 1 week, 1 month and 3 months of the formulation using the pH meter (pH ep® Hanna instrument, Padova, Italy) to check the pH stability of the formulation (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

2.3.4 Drug content of the SLMs

Formulation containing 10 mg equivalent weight of rifampicin was weighed and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask, and the volume was made up to 100 ml with 30 % methanol in distilled water. This solution was agitated for 15 minutes and filtered through a filter paper (Whatman No. 1), 1 ml of this filtrate was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up to mark with Simulated intestinal Fluid (pH 6.8) and the absorbance was measured at 475 nm using the UV visible spectrophotometer (Spectrum Lab, 752S, Breda, Netherland) The amount of drug encapsulated in the microparticles was calculated in reference to the standard Beer's plot obtained (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

2.3.5 Encapsulation efficiency

The Encapsulation Efficiency (EE %) was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{EE \%} = \frac{\text{ADC}}{\text{TDC}} \times 100 \quad \text{..... (2)}$$

Where ADC is the actual drug content and TDC the theoretical drug content (Attama *et al.*, 2009)

2.3.6 Drug loading capacity

Loading capacity (LC) expresses the ratio between the entrapped active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and the total weight of the lipids (Attama *et al.*, 2009). LC was determined using the relationship:

$$\text{LC} = \frac{\text{Amount of API Encapsulated}}{\text{Weight of Lipid}} \times 100 \quad \text{..... (3)}$$

2.3.7 Thermal analysis of the SLMs

Melting transitions and changes in heat capacity of phospholipon® 90H, *Irvingia wombolu* fat, rifampicin, lipid matrix (1:2 and 1:3) and the drug loaded SLMs were determined using a differential scanning calorimeter (Netzsch DSC 204 F1, Geratebau, GmbH, Selb, Germany). About 1.00 mg of each sample was weighed into aluminium pan, hermetically sealed and the thermal behaviour determined within the range 20–500 °C, at a heating rate of 10 K/min under a 20 ml/min nitrogen flux. The thermal properties such as melting transitions and enthalpies were noted (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

2.3.8 Stability of rifampicin in simulated gastric fluids

Stability of RMP in microspheres was monitored for 3 h using simulated gastrointestinal fluid (without pepsin) as solvent. In brief, formulation contained 10 mg equivalent of RMP were dispersed in 100 ml of SGF (S) and incubated in digital shaker

with 100 rpm at 37 °C for 3 hrs. The resultant solution and/or suspensions were filtered (using Whatman No 1) and analyzed spectrophotometrically for its stability. Percentage relative decomposition (% RD) was calculated (Satish *et al.*, 2010).

2.3.9 *In vitro* release studies

Beer's plot was obtained for rifampicin in simulated intestinal fluid (SIF, pH 6.8) and (Phosphate buffer pH 7.4) at a concentration range 0.02 – 0.10 mg/ml at a pre-determined wavelength of 475 nm. The USP paddle method was adopted in this study. The dissolution medium consisted of 250 ml of freshly prepared medium (SIF pH 6.8, pH 7.4) maintained at 37 ± 1 °C. The polycarbonate dialysis membrane (MWCO 6000–8000, Spectrum Labs, Breda, the Netherlands) selected was pre-treated by soaking in the dissolution medium for 24 h prior to use. A 50 mg quantity of the SLM was weighed from each batch and placed in a polycarbonate dialysis membrane containing 2 ml of the dissolution medium, securely tied with a thermo-resistant thread and placed in the appropriate chamber of the release apparatus. The paddle was rotated at 100 rpm, and at pre-determined timed intervals, 5 ml portions of the dissolution medium was withdrawn, appropriately diluted (10 fold dilution) and analysed for drug content in a spectrophotometer. The volume of the dissolution medium was kept constant by replacing it with 5 ml of fresh medium after each withdrawal to maintain sink condition. The amount of drug released at each time interval was determined with reference to Beer's plot (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

2.3.10 *In vitro* release kinetics (model fitting)

The dissolution data for the tablets were analysed to determine the *in vitro* release kinetic mechanism using four kinetic models including the zero order, first order equation,

Higuchi square root equation and Korsmeyer-Peppas empirical model. Drug release is said to be of first-order if it obeys the following equation:

$$\ln Q_t = \ln Q_0 - K_1 t \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where Q_t is the amount of drug released or dissolved at time t , Q_0 is amount of drug released or dissolved at time $t = 0$, k_1 is first-order release rate constant (Chime *et al.*, 2012; Singh *et al.*, 2011).

According to Higuchi relationship, the amount of drug released per unit surface area is proportional to the square root of time. This equation explains diffusion release rate as indicated below:

$$Q_t = K_H t^{1/2} \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where k_H is Higuchi rate constant, Q_t has same meaning as defined earlier (Singh *et al.*, 2011).

The integral form of Higuchi equation is employed in seeking to establish whether mixed order release kinetics exists. Diffusion controlled process is dominant where the log-log plot of the integral form of Higuchi equation approaches 0.5 (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

Korsmeyer and Peppas developed an empirical equation to analyze both Fickian and non-Fickian release of drug from swelling as well as non-swelling polymeric delivery systems. The equation is represented as:

$$M_t/M_\infty = K t^n \quad \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

where M_t/M_∞ is fraction of drug released at time t , n is diffusion exponent indicative of the mechanism of transport of drug through the polymer, K is kinetic constant (having units of t^{-n}) incorporating structural and geometric characteristics of the delivery system. The release exponent $n \leq 0.5$ for Fickian diffusion release (non swellable matrix), $0.5 < n < 1.0$ for non-Fickian release (anomalous), this means that drug release followed both diffusion and erosion controlled mechanisms and $n = 1$ for Case-II Transport (zero

order release) i.e. drug release is independent of time (Singh *et al.*, 2011), and $n > 1$ for Super Case-II transport.

2.4 Micromeritic studies

2.4.1 Bulk and tapped densities of SLMs

A 3.0 g quantity of each sample of the SLMs was weighed out and placed in a 25 ml graduated cylinder. The volume occupied by the sample was noted as the bulk volume. The bulk density was obtained by dividing the mass of the sample weighed out by the bulk volume, as shown in Equation below

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Mass of particle (M)}}{\text{Bulk Volume of Powder (Vb)}} \quad \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

The cylinder was tapped on a wooden platform by dropping the cylinder from a height of one inch at 2 seconds interval until there was no further apparent reduction in volume (Chime *et al.*, 2012).. The volume occupied by the sample was then recorded as the tapped volume. The tapped density was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{Mass of particle (M)}}{\text{Tapped Volume (VT)}} \quad \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

2.4.2 Flow rate and angle of repose (dynamic)

A funnel was properly clamped on to retort stand. The funnel orifice diameter, base diameter and efflux tube length were appropriately measured. A 3.0 g quantity of the sample was weighed out and gradually placed into the funnel with the funnel orifice closed with a shutter. The time taken for the entire sample in the funnel to flow through the orifice was noted. The flow rate was gotten by dividing the mass of the sample by the time of flow in seconds (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

The angle of repose was determined using funnel properly clamped on to retort stand. About 3.0 g of the sample was transferred and gradually placed into the funnel; the funnel orifice was closed with a shutter. The shutter was removed and the particles flowed freely forming a cone-shaped heap. The height of the sample was determined using a cathetometer; the radius was gotten by dividing the measured diameter of the formed heap on a base by two. Angle of repose (θ) for each sample was gotten using the equation:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \text{ height/radius} \quad \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

Carr's compressibility indices (%) of the lyophilized SLMs were obtained using the formula

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}-\text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100 \quad \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

Also, Hausner's ratio was obtained using Equation

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}} \quad \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

2.5 *In vivo* release studies

The animal experimental protocols were in accordance with the guidelines for conducting animal experiments stipulated by University of Nigeria, Nsukka Animal Ethics Committee. Nine albino rats weighing 180-250 g were used for the *in vivo* test. The rats were divided into two groups of three rats per group for rifampicin-loaded microparticles, sample P3 and Q3 (two samples with the highest encapsulation efficiency) and the remaining three for positive control. They were fed orally for one week for acclimatization. At the end of this period, blood was withdrawn from each of the rats (t = 0). Subsequently, 10 mg/kg of rifampicin was administered to the rats in one group while the equivalent weight of SLMs preparations was administered to the other two groups

orally (The animals had free access to water throughout the experiment). After administration, blood samples were withdrawn from the retro-orbital plexus of the rats at intervals of 1, 3, 5, 8, 18 and 24 h with the aid of heparinised capillary tubes. After withdrawal, these samples were placed in EDTA bottles and refrigerated. Thereafter, the collected blood samples were allowed to separate to obtain the top layer which is the plasma. This plasma was then diluted 5-fold with a 10 % methanol in 100 ml of distilled water solution and absorbance read using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer at the wavelength obtained (473 nm).

2.5.1 *In vitro-in vivo* correlation

The *in vitro* and *in vivo* percentage released of the drug from the two batches of rifampicin - loaded SLMs (sample P3 and Q3) used were determined each in triplicate for a period of 8 h. The *IV-IVC* graph (fraction of drug absorbed versus fraction of drug release) of the SLMs batches was used for comparison of the *in vitro* dissolution studies and the *in vivo* bioavailability studies applying the method adopted by Kuksal *et al* (Kuksal *et al.*, 2006; Uronnachi *et al.*, 2013).

2.6 Determination of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is considered the ‘gold standard’ for determining the susceptibility of organisms to antimicrobials and are therefore used to judge the performance of all other methods of susceptibility testing. The MIC is defined as the lowest concentration of a drug that will inhibit the visible growth of an organism after overnight incubation (this period is extended for organisms such as anaerobes, which require prolonged incubation for growth) (Singh *et al.*, 2011). MIC values can be determined by a number of standard test procedures. The most commonly employed methods are the tube dilution method and agar dilution methods. Serial dilutions are made

of the products in bacterial growth media. The test organisms are then added to the dilutions of the products, incubated, and scored for growth. This procedure is a standard assay for antimicrobials (EUCAST, 2000).

2.6.1 Preparation of stock solution and dilutions

About 10 mg of rifampicin was carefully weighed and dissolved in 2 ml of DMSO and made up to 10 ml with distilled water, then 10 mg equivalent of rifampicin-loaded SLMs was weighed and dissolved in 10 ml distilled water to get 1000 µg/ml. From this stock, 10 fold serial dilutions was carried out to get 100 µg/ml, from this 2 fold serial dilution to get 50 µg/ml, 25 µg/ml, 12.5 µg/ml, 6.25 µg/ml, 3.125 µg/ml for *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* MICs determination and 2 fold dilution to get 500 µg/ml, 250 µg/ml, 125 µg/ml, 62.5 µg/ml, 31.25 µg/ml for *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* MICs determinations.

2.6.2 Procedure for MIC determination

The agar diffusion method was used for the determination of the MIC, this technique depends on the ability of the antibiotic to diffuse through seeded agar at such concentration levels that can inhibit growth of the organism and thereby produce a clear zone of inhibition. The molten nutrient agar was prepared and distributed into McCartney bottles and sterilized in the autoclave at 121 °C for 15 minutes, cooled at 45 °C - 50 °C and inoculated with 0.1 ml of the broth culture organisms, mixed together and poured into a petri dish. The dish was rotated for even distribution of the cells and the agar allowed to set.

The dish was divided into four equal quarters with a marker showing boundaries, Disc of the seeded agar were removed from the agar layer with a sterile cork borer of about

8 mm in diameter in order to produce wells or cups in the agar plates. Solutions of the standard rifampicin and the rifampicin loaded SLMs (for the standard) and dilutions (for the test) were used to fill the cups. The plates were then incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. The least concentration that completely inhibited the growth of organisms was noted. For the plate which had no growth for the lowest concentration prepared, the diameters of the zone of inhibition were carefully measured. A graph of inhibition zone diameter against log concentration was plotted and extrapolated to determine the MIC.

2.7 Data and statistical analysis

The *in-vitro* release of all SLMs was computed using Microsoft Excel 2007 and the model fitting with PCP Disso v3.

CHAPTER 3

Results and discussion

3.1 Calibration curve of rifampicin

Rifampicin showed linearity with Beer's law at tested concentration range of 0.02-0.10 mg/ml (Fig. 8) with a regression coefficient of 0.970 in SIF, pH 6.8, also linearity in the concentration range of 0.02-0.12 mg/ml (Fig. 9) with a regression coefficient of 0.997 in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was observed and in plasma (Fig. 10).

Figure 8: Calibration curve for rifampicin (SIF, 6.8)

Figure 9: Calibration curve for rifampicin (phosphate buffer, pH 7.4)

Figure 10: Calibration curve for rifampicin in plasma

3.2 Particle size and morphology

Optical microscopy determines particle size, particle shape and surface characteristics simultaneously. In addition, the diameter is obtained from only two particle dimensions (i.e., length and breadth), particles must be sufficient to determine that SLMs size distribution is mono-dispersed (Washington, 1992; Martin, 2011). The photomicrographs of un-lyophilized microparticles are presented in Fig. 11 - 18. Un-lyophilized microparticles showed that the shapes of rifampicin-loaded SLMs formulated were mono-dispersed, smooth and spherical. However, crystals of rifampicin were seen to be cylindrical and some irregular. For the lyophilized microparticles Fig. 19 - 26, the shape were also spherical except that some clogged together forming compact mass of microparticles which might be as a result of lyophilization, crystals of rifampicin were seen as in un-lyophilized. From the values of particle size presented in Table 4, rifampicin-loaded SLMs diameter were within close range, the size is within 28 - 57 μm and there were no much difference between the lyophilized and un-lyophilized, but on the general, particles of the un-lyophilized had the lowest particle size. Batches of SLMs prepared with LM 1:2 exhibited the lowest mean particle size with P2 having $28 \pm 7.64 \mu\text{m}$ (un-lyophilized) and P1 and P3 having $32 \pm 7.64 \mu\text{m}$ and $37 \pm 7.64 \mu\text{m}$ respectively (lyophilized). Similarly, it was observed that the ratio of drug to lipid matrix used and the ratio/composition of the lipid matrix in the formulations have little or no effect on the particle size of the SLMs as the sizes were evenly spread or varied significantly, Some batches with lower drugs loaded in the lipid matrix at some point had higher particle sizes. The composition of the lipid matrix (phospholipon® 90H : *Irvingia wombolu* fat) had an effect on the particle size as SLMs formulated with LM 1:3 in general have the highest particle size.

Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs (un-lyophilized)

Figure 11: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; **(P1)** (before lyophilization)

Figure 12: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; **(P2)** (before lyophilization)

Figure 13: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; **(P3)** (before lyophilization)

Figure 14: Photomicrograph of unloaded SLMs; **(P4)** (before lyophilization)

Figure 15: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; **(Q1)** (before lyophilization)

Figure 16: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; **(Q2)** (before lyophilization)

Figure 17: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; (Q3) (before lyophilization)

Figure 18: Photomicrograph of unloaded SLMs; (Q4) (before lyophilization)

Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs (lyophilized)

Figure 19: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; (P1) (after lyophilization)

Figure 20: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; (P2) (after lyophilization)

Figure 21: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; (P3) (after lyophilization)

Figure 22: Photomicrograph of unloaded SLMs; (P4) (after lyophilization)

Figure 23: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; (Q1) (after lyophilization)

Figure 24: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; (Q2) (after lyophilization)

Figure 25: Photomicrograph of rifampicin loaded SLMs; (Q3) (after lyophilization)

Figure 26: Photomicrograph of unloaded SLMs; (Q4) (after lyophilization)

The results also indicated that the encapsulated drug is in the inner core of the SLMs, this is the possible reason for increased particle size seen in SLMs formulated with LM 1:3 (un-lyophilized) which contain higher *Irvingia wombolu* fat. Particle size may be a function of either one or more of the following: formulation excipient, degree of homogenisation, homogenisation pressure, rate of particle size growth, crystalline habit of the particle etc (Chime *et al.*, 2012; Attama *et al.*, 2009).

Table 4: Physicochemical properties of rifampicin-loaded SLMs

Batch	pH (unlyophilized)				Percentage recovery (%)	Particle size		LC (%)	TDC (%)	ADC (% ± SD)	EE (%)
	24 hrs	1 weeks	1 month	3 months		(un-lyophilized) (µm ± SD)	(lyophilized) (µm ± SD)				
P1	5.3 ± 0.07	5.2 ± 0.14	5.2 ± 0.00	5.2 ± 0.14	73.3	45 ± 18.58	32 ± 7.64	16.9	1.00	0.85 ± 0.02	84.7
P2	5.2 ± 0.07	5.3 ± 0.07	5.4 ± 0.07	5.3 ± 0.00	82.5	28 ± 7.64	53 ± 7.64	34.7	2.00	1.73 ± 0.03	86.7
P3	5.3 ± 0.14	5.0 ± 0.28	4.8 ± 0.28	4.6 ± 0.10	85.0	50 ± 10.00	37 ± 7.64	45.8	2.50	2.29 ± 0.02	91.6
P4	5.7 ± 0.21	5.8 ± 0.07	5.7 ± 0.07	5.4 ± 0.28	69.1	50 ± 5.00	42 ± 12.58	-	-	-	-
Q1	5.2 ± 0.14	5.4 ± 0.14	5.7 ± 0.07	5.6 ± 0.07	88.1	42 ± 7.64	55 ± 26.46	16.6	1.00	0.83 ± 0.01	82.9
Q2	5.4 ± 0.21	5.1 ± 0.21	4.6 ± 0.00	4.8 ± 0.21	84.6	42 ± 14.43	43 ± 18.93	33.8	2.00	1.69 ± 0.04	84.5
Q3	5.2 ± 0.00	5.3 ± 0.07	5.4 ± 0.35	5.4 ± 0.14	79.1	42 ± 7.64	50 ± 5.00	43.5	2.50	2.17 ± 0.03	87.0
Q4	5.4 ± 0.07	5.3 ± 0.14	5.1 ± 0.14	5.2 ± 0.00	86.2	57 ± 7.64	45 ± 15.00	-	-	-	-

NB: P1–P3 contains LM 1:2, Q1–Q3, LM 1:3 and varied concentrations of rifampicin, while P4 and Q4 contain no API.

3.3: Percentage recovery of SLMs

The percentage of the SLMs recovered from the formulations presented in Table 4 and Fig. 28 indicates that all the rifampicin loaded SLMs exhibited overall higher percentage recovery.

Figure 27: Percentage yield of microparticles

Batches P1, P2 and P3 prepared with lipid matrix comprising of phospholipon® 90H and *Irvingia wombolu* fat in the ratio of 1:2 showed high percentage recovery more than the unloaded while only Q1 showed percentage recovery more than the unloaded for LM 1:3. Batches of SLMs prepared with lipid matrix 1:2 showed percentage recovery ranging from 69 - 85 % while those produced with lipid matrix 1:3 is between 79 - 88.1 %. P3 and Q1 had percentage recovery of more than 85 %.

3.4 Time-dependent pH stability studies of the formulations

Change in pH could be a function of degradation of the API or excipient. A prior stable API may be affected by degradation of excipient with storage through generation of unfavourable pH (increase or decrease) or reactive species for the API (Chime *et al.*, 2012). A 1% suspension of rifampicin in water has a pH of 4.5 - 6.5 (Gallo *et al.*, 1976). From the results of pH of rifampicin loaded SLMs presented in Table 4, all the batches of the SLMs preparation including the unloaded have a pH that is within range. Based on this, issue of degradation of rifampicin was ruled out although batch P3 have a pH which is as low as 4.6 ± 0.10 and Q2 4.8 ± 0.21 . There were some fluctuations in the pH for few batches but this could be as result of the calibration of the pH meter. The pH for all the batches ranges from 4.6 - 5.7 and there were slight decline in the pH readings. However, the slight decline in the pH values in most SLM formulations cannot be attributed to drug degradation since there was also a fall in the pH of the unloaded SLMs.

3.5 Encapsulation efficiency

Drug encapsulation efficiency is a test performed to determine the amount of drug that is actually retained in the microparticles, usually expressed as a percentage. It goes a long way to show the reliability or otherwise, of the formulation technique (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012). The drug content was estimated to confirm that there is no degradation of the drug and the expected amount of drug is present in the product.

Figure 28: Encapsulation efficiency of SLMs

Encapsulation efficiency of drug-loaded SLMs was found to be in the range of 82.9 - 91.6 % (Table 4, Fig. 27). Encapsulation efficiency was dependent on the composition of drug as well as the lipid matrix. Low content of *Irvingia wombolu* fat in lipid matrix (LM 1:2) and high composition of drug in formulation resulted with high encapsulation of drug in SLMs formulations. Lipid matrix ratio of 1:2 yielded maximum encapsulation efficiency of 91.6 %, whereas minimum encapsulation efficiency of 82.9 % was observed with 1:3 ratio of lipid matrix. However, rifampicin being a low solubility drug with high dose required low concentration of lipids and/or excipient in dosage form for better formulation development. In general all the batches recorded high encapsulation efficiency above 80 %; further research is required to improve the biopharmaceutical properties of rifampicin using solid lipid microparticles.

3.6 Drug loading capacity

The selection of a drug carrier system and its effectiveness in the encapsulation of a drug depends on the loading capacity of the carrier system (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012). The loading capacity of the SLMs batches is found on Table 4 with P3 (LC - 45.8 %) of LM 1:2 having the highest LC corresponding to its encapsulation efficiency (has the highest EE %). Some of the factors which affect the loading capacity of a drug in a lipid are the solubility of the drug in the lipid melt, the miscibility of the drug in the lipid melt, the chemical and physical orientation of the solid lipid matrix, and the polymorphic state of the lipid material (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012).

3.7 Thermal analysis

This characterisation step is necessary in order to detect possible modifications (or incompatibility) in the physicochemical properties of the drug incorporated into SLMs and of the lipophilic excipient.

Figure 29: DSC thermogram of phospholipon 90H

Figure 30: DSC thermogram of Rifampicin

Figure 31: DSC thermogram of *Irvingia wombolus* fat

Figure 32: DSC thermogram of Lipid Matrix 1:2

Figure 33: DSC thermogram of Lipid Matrix 1:3

Figure 34: DSC thermogram of Sample P3

Figure 35: DSC thermogram of Sample Q3

It has been proved that although particles were produced from crystalline raw materials, the presence of emulsifiers, the preparation method and the high-shear dispersion may result to changes in the crystallinity of matrix constituents compared with bulk materials. This may lead to liquid, amorphous or only partially crystallised metastable systems (Jaspart *et al.*, 2005). Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is one of the most widely used techniques to study solid state, and especially to determine compound purity, stability and polymorphism (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012). DSC technique relies on the principle that solid-state modifications are characterised by different melting points and melting enthalpies (Mehnert *et al.*, 2001). DSC indeed measures transition temperatures (solidification and melting temperatures, glass transition temperature, and thermal degradation temperature) as well as transition enthalpies (Martin, 2011).

DSC measurements were carried out in order to determine the thermal properties of rifampicin, phospholipon® 90H, *Irvingia wombolu* fat, lipid matrix 1:2 and 1:3 and SLMs batch P3 and Q3 (two formulation with highest EE %). The results of DSC presented in Fig. 29 above showed that the DSC curve of phospholipon® 90H showed a curve with the melting peak at temperature of 124 °C. The curve shows that phospholipon® 90H consist entirely of stable form because of the sharp melting peak seen. *Irvingia wombolu* fat showed a narrow sharp endothermic peak, with melting peak at temperature 42.3 °C (Fig. 30). The narrow melting peak indicated that *Irvingia wombolu* fat is a high purity lipid. This implies low drug holding capacity of the unmodified lipid. The DSC results of the lipid matrices showed melting peaks at 76.9 °C and 72.1 °C respectively for LM 1:2 (Fig. 32), 1:3 (Fig. 33). The results showed that structuring of P90H and *Irvingia wombolu* fat generally produced matrices with low enthalpies than P90H. Reduction in enthalpy generally suggests less crystallinity of lipid matrices (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, LM 1:2 and 1:3 generated imperfect matrices (due to distortion of crystal arrangement of

individual lipids after melting and solidification), which may have created numerous spaces for drug localization (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012; Chime *et al.*, 2012). The varied fatty acid contents of these lipids may have interacted in such a manner as to partly disorder the crystal arrangement of the individual lipids (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012).

Rifampicin exhibits two polymorphic forms, i.e. form I and form II (Stanley *et al.*, 2001). It also exists as hydrates and various solvates, which are eventually converted into amorphous form at room temperature or after dissolution (Ramesh *et al.*, 2006). RMP form II, which is meta-stable, melts at 189°C and re-crystallize as a form I at 204 °C. RMP form I has lower chemical stability at higher temperature and hence it decompose before melting at 258 °C. Amorphous RMP shows exothermic peak, which starts at 196 °C, indicating the crystallization of form I and subsequent peak at 258 °C representing the decomposition of RMP form I (Agrawal *et al.*, 2004; Satish *et al.*, 2010). DSC thermogram of RMP is shown in Fig. 30. DSC thermogram of the pure RMP showed endothermic broad bend between 180 °C and 190 °C, which represented the melting of form II and subsequently exothermic peak at 252.9 °C revealed the crystallization of form I. Melting peaks showed that rifampicin used was pure and crystalline, as this is comparable to the melting point reported for rifampicin in monograph (Drug-bank: Rifampicin; DB01045). Endothermic peak 200 -220 °C revealed the decomposition to form I. Thermal behaviour of RMP obtained from DSC data confirmed that RMP used in present study exists as form II. When the lipid matrices were employed to formulate SLMs, the DSC traces of the formulations showed various peaks according to drug and the composition of lipid matrix. DSC thermogram of RMP loaded microparticles (Fig. 34 – 35) exhibited broad rounded exothermic peak (disappearance of RMP Peak) from DSC thermogram of rifampicin-loaded microparticles batches P3 and Q3. This indicates that the major portion of RMP in SLMs exists in amorphous form. It was also observed that the

two batches gave lower enthalpies. The broad rounded peak at the end of the curve also indicates the reduction in crystallinity of the system. However, solubilization of low amount of drug in the molten lipid while the sample is heating and having low amount of drug in the formulation makes it difficult to effectively record the melting peak of incorporated drug in the formulation (Jaspart *et al.*, 2007, Chime *et al.*, 2012). The study revealed that hot homogenisation method for preparation of RMP microparticles altered the crystalline nature of RMP. Solid-state stability of RMP is the major problem for poor bioavailability of RMP in dosage forms. Solubility and dissolution studies in reported literatures revealed that there is no statistically significant difference in solubility and dissolution between two forms of RMP (Agrawal *et al.*, 2004). Moreover, form I is also present in commercial dosage forms and hence there was no impact of change in polymorphic form during formulation development on solubility and dissolution. However, chemical stability of RMP in dosage form is an important critical issue, which can affect the biopharmaceutical quality of dosage form. Hot homogenisation method for preparation of RMP microspheres was found to be ideal and has no impact on chemical stability of rifampicin.

3.8 Stability of RMP in SGF

The purpose of current research work was also to determine if rifampicin-loaded microparticles can improve the stability of RMP in presence of gastric fluid. In order to find out the stability of RMP in stomach, SGF without pepsin (Dressman *et al.*, 2005) was used as a medium for determination of relative decomposition of RMP over the period of 3 hours.

Figure 36: Stability studies in SGF

Decomposition of RMP in SLMs was less than that of pure drug (Fig. 36). The low percentage decomposition of 7.6 % and 14.3% was achieved with Batch P3 and Q3 (batches with highest EE %) as against 38.3 % of pure RMP. Moreover, drug decomposition in microspheres was dependent on the composition of lipid matrix. LM ratio of 1:2 showed maximum stability of RMP in SGF. Stability studies of RMP revealed that SLMs reduced the drug decomposition and hence improved the stability of drug in stomach.

3.9 Micromeritic properties

Micromeritics is the study of particles, particle behaviour and their functionality in pharmaceutical formulation. In the area of tablet and capsule manufacture, control of particle size is essential in achieving the necessary flow properties and proper mixing of granules and powders (Martins, 2011). The measurement of the flow properties of powders is essential before capsule filling because variation in particle flow will automatically cause variation in capsule weight and active ingredient variation. The flow property of bulk material results from the cohesive forces acting on individual particles such as Van der Waals, electrostatic, surface tension, interlocking, and friction (Onyishi *et al.*, 2013). The flow of powder during manufacturing dictates the quality of the product in terms of weight and content uniformity of the capsules (Onyishi *et al.*, 2013). The results of the flow properties of rifampicin-loaded microparticles are shown in Table 5. The flow properties of the formulations were determined using both the direct and the indirect methods of assessing flow of particles (Aulton, 2007; Ngwuluka *et al.*, 2010, Chime *et al.*, 2012). Particle fluidity is important in capsule filling because variability in flow rate will automatically cause variability in capsule filled weight and active ingredient variation.

Table 5: Micromeritic properties of lyophilized SLMs

Batch	Bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose (°)	Flow rate (g/s)
P1	0.240 ± 0.57	0.333 ± 0.14	27.993	1.389	34.06 ± 0.85	0.06 ± 7.19
P2	0.200 ± 0.42	0.273 ± 0.28	26.659	1.364	30.41 ± 0.28	0.05 ± 1.36
P3	0.231 ± 0.28	0.316 ± 0.28	26.916	1.368	35.30 ± 0.14	0.06 ± 0.25
Q1	0.200 ± 0.42	0.231 ± 0.57	13.345	1.154	18.42 ± 0.42	0.15 ± 1.58
Q2	0.231 ± 0.14	0.300 ± 0.85	23.067	1.300	36.43 ± 0.28	0.05 ± 2.16
Q3	0.261 ± 0.57	0.316 ± 0.14	17.384	1.210	31.88 ± 0.57	0.05 ± 0.31

NB: P1–P3 contains LM 1:2, Q1–Q3, LM 1:3 and varied concentrations of rifampicin, Mean ± SD, n – 3

The results of loosed densities (bulk and tapped densities) showed that the microparticles had reduced densities and hence had a poor flow with the exception of batch Q3 which had a passable flow. Bulk and tapped densities are important, because they are used as an indirect method of assessing powder flow. A reduction in bulk density may be associated with a reduction in particle size and a loose packed powder bed which is unlikely to flow because of inherent cohesiveness of the fine particles (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

Hausner's ratio value less than 1.25 indicates good flow (= 20% Carr), powder with low interparticle friction, such as coarse spheres. Value greater than 1.5 indicates poor flow (= 33% Carr), more cohesive, less free-flowing powders such as flakes. Between 1.25 and 1.5, added glidant normally improves flow. > 1.5 added glidant doesn't improve flow (Aulton, 2007). Therefore batches Q1 and Q4 SLMs had good flow while the other batches P1, P2, P3 of LM 1:2 and Q2 of LM 1:3 that have Hausner's ratio between 1.25 and 1.5 needs the addition of glidant to improve flow. Also, Carr's compressibility index in the range of 5 – 15 indicates excellent flow, 16 – 18 good flow, 19 – 21 fair flow, 22 –

35 poor flow, 36 – 40 very poor flow and > 40 extremely poor flow (Aulton, 2007). Batches Q1 and Q3 containing LM 1:3 and loaded with 1 % and 2.5 % rifampicin exhibited good flow while the other batches P1, P2, P3 of LM 1:2 and Q2 of LM 1:3 that have Carr's index between 22 – 35 had poor flow. Flow rate of rifampicin-loaded SLMs was affected by the ratio/composition of the LM used in the formulation as the batches belonging to the LM 1:3 (more of *Irvingia wombolu* fat) had good flow.

The frictional forces in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose θ . θ = the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of powder and horizontal plane = coefficient of friction μ between the particles. Angle of repose less than 20 is termed (excellent flow), 20-30 (good flow), 30-34 (Pass flow) and greater than 40 (poor flow) (Martins, 2011). The rougher and more irregular the surface of the particles, the higher will be the angle of repose (Martins, 2011). Angle of repose was used as an indirect method of assessing flow of powder; because of their relationship with inter particle cohesion (Chime *et al.*, 2012). The result of angle of repose showed that the SLMs had poor flow. Only Batch Q1 with angle of repose less than 20 showed excellent flow. Batches P2 and Q3 had angle of repose between 30-34 which could be termed as passable flow while other have showed angle of repose above 34 which indicates poor flow. The results of flow rate (that is, flow under gravity) showed that the microparticles had poor flow or can best be described as not flowable. However, the factors that can affect the flow rate of particles include particle size, particle size distribution, particle shape, particle density, particle cohesion and relative humidity of the environment among others (Aulton, 2007). The flow rate of the SLMs can be improved by reducing the ratio of triglyceride in the formulation, addition of glidants (which will reduce the inter-particulate friction and increase the flow of the lyophilized SLMs) and proper storage of SLMs in a moisture resistant container (Chime *et al.*, 2012).

3.10 *In vitro* drug release studies

In vitro release of rifampicin from SLMs was evaluated using a dialysis membrane diffusion technique. Dialysis membranes were cut and filled with 50 mg of SLMs dispersion and immersed in 250 ml dissolution medium using a dissolution rate test apparatus and magnetic stirrer assembly rotated at 100 rpm. The *in vitro* release studies were performed in simulated intestinal fluid (SIF), pH 6.8 and phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 as dissolution media in order to avoid acid decomposition of rifampicin in presence of HCl in stomach. The rate and extent of decomposition of rifampicin in HCl may affect the quantification of release kinetics of rifampicin in dissolution medium (Satish *et al.*, 2010). *In vitro* drug release profile is an important tool that predicts in advance how the drug will behave *in vivo* (Umeyor *et al.*, 2012). The *in vitro* dissolution studies of the SLMs prepared by hot homogenisation method were carried out up to period of 12 hours. The *in vitro* release data were evaluated based on percentage drug release Vs time profile and *in vitro* release kinetics was determined. Sink condition was maintained throughout the study.

The *in vitro* release data of rifampicin-loaded SLMs is presented as follows; 1) Batch P1, P2 and P3 in Fig. 37 - 43. 2) Batch Q1, Q2 and Q3 in Fig. 44 - 50 for simulated intestinal fluid (SIF, pH 6.8) respectively. 3) Batch P1, P2 and P3 in Fig. 51 - 57 and 4) batch Q1, Q2 and Q3 in Fig. 58 - 64 for phosphate buffer, pH 7.4. Also the *in vitro* release for branded rifampicin A and B for both media are presented in Fig. 65 - 68. The corresponding dissolution profiles (with model fitting) of all SLMs prepared are shown in figures mentioned earlier respectively.

SLMs showed different onset of drug release; the release rate of rifampicin-loaded SLMs prepared with varying ratios of lipid matrices showed gradual release of the drug. At 15 minutes (T15), less than 5 % of the drug was released from batches P2, P3, Fig. 39 and 41 respectively (loaded with 2 % and 3 % drug) and batches Q1, Q2 Fig. 44 and 46

respectively (loaded with 1 % and 2 % of drug) in SIF, 6.8 with exception of P1, Fig. 37 (loaded with 1 %) of LM 1:2 and Q3, Fig. 48 (loaded with 1 %) of LM 1:3 which had releases of 11.4 % and 8.3 % at T15 respectively. All the batches in phosphate buffer had releases more than 5 % at 15 minutes; batch P1, P2, P3, Fig. 51, 53 and 55 respectively (LM 1:2) had 7.6 %, 15.5 % and 10.1 % while Q1, Q2 and Q3, Fig. 58, 60 and 62 respectively had release rates of 10.6 %, 11.0 %, and 7.9 %.

***In vitro* release in simulated intestinal fluid**

Figure 37: *In-vitro* release, SIF, pH 6.8 (P1)

Figure 38: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, SIF, pH 6.8 (P1)

Figure 39: *In-vitro* release, SIF, pH 6.8 (P2)

Figure 40: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, SIF, pH 6.8 (P2)

Figure 41: *In-vitro* release, SIF, pH 6.8 (P3)

Figure 42: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, SIF, pH 6.8 (P3)

Figure 43: Comparative release profile of rifampicin loaded SLMs (LM ratio, 1:2); SIF: pH 6.8

Figure 44: *In-vitro* release, SIF, pH 6.8 (Q1)

Figure 45: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, SIF, pH 6.8 (Q1)

Figure 46: *In-vitro* release, SIF, pH 6.8 (Q2)

Figure 47: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, SIF, pH 6.8 (Q2)

Figure 48: *In-vitro* release, SIF, pH 6.8 (Q3)

Figure 49: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, SIF, pH 6.8 (Q3)

Figure 50: Comparative release profile of rifampicin loaded SLMS (LM ratio, 1:3); SIF: pH 6.8

In-vitro release, phosphate buffer

Figure 51: *In-vitro* release, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (P1)

Figure 52: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (P1)

Figure 53: *In-vitro* release, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (P2)

Figure 54: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (P2)

Figure 55: *In-vitro* release, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (P3)

Figure 56: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (P3)

Figure 57: Comparative release profile of rifampicin loaded SLMS (LM ratio, 1:2), phosphate buffer; pH 7.4

Figure 58: *In-vitro* release, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (Q1)

Figure 59: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (Q1)

Figure 60: *In-vitro* release, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (Q2)

Figure 61: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (Q2)

Figure 62: *In-vitro* release, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (Q3)

Figure 63: *In-vitro* release with model fitting, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (Q3)

Figure 64: Comparative release profile of rifampicin loaded SLMS (LM ratio, 1:3), phosphate buffer; pH 7.4

Figure 65: *In vitro* release, branded rifampicin A (SIF, pH 6.8)

Figure 66: *In vitro* release, branded rifampicin B (SIF, pH 6.8)

Figure 67: *In vitro* release, branded rifampicin A (phosphate buffer, pH 7.4)

Figure 68: *In vitro* release, branded rifampicin B (phosphate buffer, pH 7.4)

The rifampicin-loaded SLMs in all the batches had a higher sustained-release effect than the market brand. Rifampicin market brand showed maximum release at 3 hours, while maximum release rate for rifampicin-loaded SLMs could not be reached at 12 hour in all the formulations. Batches P1, P2, P3 of LM 1:2 had 73.1 %, 67.6 % and 66.7 % release rates respectively at the 12 h while batch Q1, Q2, Q3 had release rates of 90.0 %, 69.2 %, and 71.9 % at same hour both in simulated intestinal fluid, pH 6.8. For the release in phosphate buffer, batches P1, P2, and P3 of LM 1:2 had 81.1 %, 76.1 %, and 66.2 % release rates respectively at the 12 h while batch Q1, Q2, Q3 had release rates of 76.3 %, 69.1 % and 65.4 % at same hour. Between 65.4 – 81.1 % of the drug was released at 12 h in all the rifampicin-loaded SLM formulations. However, SLMs formulated with LM 1:2 and loaded with 1 % rifampicin (batch P2) had 90.0 % of rifampicin released at same hour. The order of drug release retardation with different ratios in both media was $P3 > P2 > P1$ as observed in case of LM 1:2 and same for batch Q.

The comparative release profiles of rifampicin-loaded-loaded SLMs are shown in Fig. 42, 49 for batch P and Q in SIF, pH 6.8 and Fig. 56, 63 for phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 respectively. Further, the over all in vitro results indicated that, rifampicin-loaded SLMs in SIF, pH 6.8 gave higher rate of drug release compared to release in phosphate buffer. In phosphate buffer there was more retarded release. For the composition of the lipid matrix, there was variability in drug release rate but LM 1:3 had more retarded release when both lipid matrix compositions are compared. This could be explained based on porosity and tortuosity of *Irvingia wombolu* fat. Usually, as the concentration of lipid increases the coating level also increases (Chime *et al.*, 2012). It has been reported by many authors that the increase in lipid/polymer content decreases the total porosity (initial porosity plus porosity due to the dissolution of the drug) and also increases the tortuosity of the matrix and diffusion path length. This in turn slows down diffusion and erosion of matrix

resulting in retardation of drug release (Boza *et al.*, 1999; Lee *et al.*, 1999; Chime *et al.*, 2012). The drug's physicochemical characteristics (its water solubility) also play a part. The release rate and the amount of drug released from SLMs decreased with drug hydrophobicity. The preparation method of the SLMs can affect the drug's release rate by influencing the matrix wettability properties. The particle size is also considered as a relevant parameter influencing drug release. Drug release from smaller particles is higher than release from larger ones because of the larger specific surface area of smaller microparticles (Jaspart *et al.*, 2005). Consequently, a suitable choice of SLMs formulation (in terms of excipient nature, drug nature and drug loading) can bring about the intended *in vitro* release profiles (e.g., sustained release, enhanced release (Jaspart *et al.*, 2005).

The *in vitro* drug dissolution studies revealed that rifampicin-loaded SLMs formulated by hot homogenisation method using phospholipon® 90H and *Irvingia wombolu* fat can be used to prepare sustained release dosage form of rifampicin for improving biopharmaceutical characteristics of rifampicin.

3.11 *In vitro* release kinetics

The *in vitro* drug release data were analyzed with various models such as first order, Higuchi release mode and zero order. The data obtained were also put in Korsmeyer-Peppas model in order to find out "n" value, which describes the drug release mechanism. The release correlation coefficient "R²"s of first-order, Higuchi, zero order and "n" values of Korsmeyer-Peppas model of rifampicin-loaded SLMs are summarized in Table 6 (medium SIF, pH 6.8) and 7 (medium, phosphate buffer, pH 7.4) respectively. The release pattern of batch P1, P2 of LM 1:2 and Q3 of LM 1:3 showed best fit into the Korsmeyer-Peppas model. P3 and Q1 both of LM 1:2 showed best fit into first-order and Q2 of LM 1:3 fitted to the zero order with highest "R²" (correlation coefficient) values as reference (all in SIF, pH 6.8). For release in phosphate buffer P1, P2, P3, Q1 showed best

fit into the Korsmeeyer-Peppas model while Q2 and Q3 showed best fit into the Higuchi release model with highest "R²" (correlation coefficient) values as reference.

Table 6: *In vitro* release kinetics of rifampicin from SLMs (Media: SIF, pH 6.8)

Batch	Zero order	1 st order	Higuchi	Korsmeeyer-Peppas		
	R ²			R ²	n	Order of release
P1	0.9028	0.9636	0.9722	0.9757	0.4377	Fickian
P2	0.9463	0.9900	0.9900	0.9964	0.5682	Non-Fickian
P3	0.9695	0.9807	0.9691	0.9614	0.8502	Non-Fickian
Q1	0.9585	0.9907	0.9811	0.9806	0.8179	Non-Fickian
Q2	0.9857	0.9805	0.9496	0.9523	0.8786	Non-Fickian
Q3	0.9175	0.9861	0.9949	0.9968	0.5825	Non-Fickian

Table 7: *In vitro* release kinetics of rifampicin from SLMs (Media: phosphate buffer, pH 7.4)

Batch	Zero order	1 st order	Higuchi	Korsmeeyer-Peppas		
	R ²			R ²	n	Order of release
P1	0.8341	0.9567	0.9829	0.9831	0.6126	Non-Fickian
P2	0.6455	0.8922	0.9648	0.9895	0.4073	Fickian
P3	0.6629	0.8709	0.9681	0.9745	0.4353	Fickian
Q1	0.6922	0.9069	0.9719	0.9776	0.4599	Fickian
Q2	0.9085	0.9793	0.9924	0.9912	0.4555	Fickian
Q3	0.6512	0.8467	0.9613	0.9607	0.4771	Fickian

The value of release exponent "n" determined from rifampicin-loaded SLMs ranged from 0.4377 to 0.8786 in SIF, pH 6.8 and 0.4073 to 0.6126 in phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 respectively. A good fit to the Korsmeeyer-Peppas equation indicated a combined

effect of diffusion and erosion mechanisms for drug release from prepared SLMs (Korsmeyer *et al.*, 1983). In simulated intestinal fluid only batch P1 showed Fickian diffusion (Higuchi Matrix), while other formulations exhibited non-Fickian diffusion (i.e. a combination of the diffusion and erosion mechanisms) sustained release as the "n" values fell between the limiting values of Fickian and Case II transport (i.e. > 0.45 but < 1.0). Drug leaching occurs as the dissolution medium penetrates the lipid matrix through pores, cracks and inter-granular spaces as well as erosion of the matrix which is facilitated by the saponification of fatty acid by the alkaline dissolution medium (Suneel, 2011). In phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 all the formulations showed Fickian diffusion (Higuchi matrix) with the exception of P1 which exhibited non-Fickian diffusion (i.e. a combination of the diffusion and erosion mechanisms) sustained release. Therefore, the release mechanisms studied showed that rifampicin-loaded SLMs had mixed mechanisms of release with diffusion controlled and first-order release models as the predominant mechanism of release in all the batches.

3.12 *In vivo* release properties

From biopharmaceutical standpoint, correlation could be referred to as the relationship between appropriate *in-vitro* release characteristics and *in vivo* bioavailability parameters. United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) defined it as the establishment of a rational relationship between a biological property and a parameter derived from a biological property produced by a dosage form, and a physicochemical property or characteristic of the same dosage form (USP, 2004). Food and Drug Administration (FDA) defined *in vitro-in vivo* correlation (IV-IVC) as a predictive mathematical model describing the relationship between an *in vitro* property of a dosage form and a relevant *in vivo* response. Generally, the *in vitro* property is the rate or extent of drug dissolution or release while the *in vivo* response is the plasma drug concentration or amount of drug

absorbed (FDA, 1997). An IV-IVC is expected only in the case of Class II drugs though IV-IVC could be expected for Class I drugs if the dissolution rate is slower than the gastric emptying rate; with a sufficiently rapidly dissolving Class I drug, little or no IV-IVC is expected because gastric emptying (not dissolution) would be the rate limiting step (Larry and Mark, 2002; Uronnachi *et al.*, 2013).

Plasma concentration and pharmacokinetic parameters after oral administration of formulated SLMs and conventional rifampicin are summarized in Figure 70. Rifampicin is well absorbed following oral absorption, its peak concentration in the plasma is 10 µg/ml in 2 - 4 hours. No sustained blood level of rifampicin was evident after oral administration of the conventional form. Although, plasma concentration-time profile was characterized by significantly higher plasma concentration after 2 - 3 hours of administration, and then the plasma concentration declined rapidly. The formulated SLMs (batch P3 and Q3) showed significantly lower maximum concentration than rifampicin. The *in vivo* findings revealed that the SLMs batches have their absorption peaked at 3rd hour, however, these SLMs maintained constant plasma concentration up to 18 hours. The smooth and extended absorption phase coupled with maintenance of plasma concentration for longer duration after administration in formulated SLMs batches can help reduce chance of dose-dependent side effects of rifampicin.

Figure 70: Cumulative *in vivo* release data

3.13 *In vitro-in vivo* correlation

In Fig. 70 - 71 the IV-IVC graph (fraction of drug absorbed versus fraction of drug release) of the SLMs batches loaded with 2.5 % of drug (P3 and Q3) according to Kuksal *et al* (Kuksal *et al.*, 2006) showed a level-A correlation with a regression coefficient of 0.916 and 0.913 respectively.

The *in vitro-in vivo* correlation determined gave credence that a good correlation exists between the dissolution profiles and bioavailability respectively; this can serve as a biomarker for clinical investigations. This showed to a reasonable extent that the *in vitro* data of the SLMs batches could be used to predict the *in vivo* properties of the formulation. With the Level A correlation established, it is possible that *in vitro* testing may be utilized for establishing the effects of manufacturing modifications such as minor formulation changes, manufacturing site and equipment change, alternative excipient suppliers, and a change in dosage form strength in the same formulation.

Figure 71: *In vitro* - *in vivo* correlation, batch P3

Figure 72: *In vitro* - *in vivo* correlation, batch Q3

3.14 Result of the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs)

Minimum inhibitory concentrations are important in diagnostic laboratories to confirm resistance of micro-organisms to an antimicrobial agent and also to monitor the activity of new antimicrobial agents. An MIC is generally regarded as the most basic laboratory measurement of the activity of an antimicrobial agent against an organism. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is the lowest concentration of an antimicrobial that will inhibit the visible growth of a microorganism after overnight incubation (EUCAST, 2000). Effects of rifampicin-loaded microparticles encapsulation and storage on the biological activity of the formulated drug were studied by an antibacterial assay using agar diffusion method. The assay measured growth inhibition of the test organisms. The determination of IZD using agar plate method is based on the diffusion of an antibiotic agent or formulation thereof through a solidified nutrient agar. The minimum inhibition concentration for all the batches of the rifampicin-loaded SLMs and pure rifampicin is summarised in Table 8.

Table 8: MIC for different batches ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Organisms	Batch						
	P1	P2	P3	Q1	Q2	Q3	RMP
	($\mu\text{g/ml}$)						
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0.0316	0.02	0.0079	0.02	0.0398	0.02	0.005
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	25	6.25	12.5	12.5	6.25	3.125	6.125
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	62.5	62.5	125	125	62.5	31.25	62.5
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	500	250	500	1000	500	250	125

Rifampicin inhibits the growth of most gram-positive bacteria as well as many gram-negative microorganisms such as *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas*, indole-positive

and indole-negative *Proteus*, and *Klebsiella*. Rifampicin is very active against *Staphylococcus aureus* and coagulase-negative staphylococci. The effect of the SLMs formulations on the test organism gave the zones of inhibition in decreasing order of magnitude of $Sa > Bs > Ec > Kp$. There was no zone of inhibition in unloaded SLMs (result not shown). This indicates that all the test formulations containing the rifampicin, retained its antibacterial potential and demonstrated significantly greater zone of inhibition. Batch Q3 was very much active against *S.aureus* as compared to other test organisms; when compared to the rest of the formulations, it is worthy of noting that, the lipid base has effect on the release of the loaded drug. Batch Q3, shows that more of the drug was accommodated in the SLMs, hence the increase in the release and subsequently, more effect on *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Batch P2 and Q1 showed a similar effect on *S. aureus*. Batch Q3 effectiveness in *E. coli* and *S. aureus* than other test organisms, may be associated to the increase in the lipid base used. In general, rifampicin-loaded microparticles were very effective and retained their bioactivity. The present work suggests that the highly hydrophobic rifampicin can be entrapped with acceptable efficiency into SLMs and drug bioactivity maintained as observed in the MIC studies.

CHAPTER 4

Conclusion and recommendation

Lipid microparticles drug delivery technology presents significant opportunities for improving medical therapeutics, but the technology's potential remains unrealized. From the present research work, it can be concluded that the formulation of rifampicin-loaded microparticles is a novel approach to eliminate variability in bioavailability and also prepare sustained release rifampicin formulations.

Solid lipid microparticles (SLMs) of rifampicin using phospholipon® 90H and fat from *Irvingia wombolu* were successfully prepared by hot homogenization method with lipid matrix in the ratio of 1:2 and 1:3. The SLMs prepared were found to be fine and drug content of all prepared SLMs of rifampicin was uniform. The particle size of the SLMs was found in the range of 28 - 88 um as there were no much difference between the lyophilized and un-lyophilized and the composition of the lipid matrix (phospholipon® 90H : *Irvingia wombolu*) had an effect on the particle size as SLMs formulated with LM 1:3 in general have the highest particle size. The photomicrographs of SLMs of un-lyophilized microparticles showed that the shapes of rifampicin-loaded SLMs formulated were mono-dispersed, smooth and spherical. For the lyophilized microparticles, the shapes were also spherical except that some clogged together forming compact mass of microparticles which might be as a result of lyophilization. The pH for all the batches was in the range of 4.6 - 5.7 and there were slight decline in the pH readings. The microencapsulation efficiency was relatively high, encapsulation efficiency of drug-loaded SLMs were found to be in the range of 82.9 - 91.6 % and was dependent on the composition of drug as well as the lipid matrix. The present study was also aimed to develop the rifampicin-loaded microparticles that can prevent decomposition of RMP in presence of gastric fluid and the stability of rifampicin in *in-vitro* environments. DSC

studies confirmed that the major portion of drug was in form II. However, small trace of form I found in DSC thermogram demonstrated the phase transition (form II to form I) of rifampicin during SLMs formation. The study revealed that hot homogenisation method for preparation of RMP microparticles altered the crystalline nature of RMP and was found to be ideal method of RMP SLMs formulation as it has no impact on chemical stability of rifampicin. The micromeritic studies showed that the microparticles had poor flow or can best be described as not flowable but can be improved by reducing the ratio of triglyceride in the formulation, addition of glidants and proper storage of SLMs in a moisture resistant container. The *in vitro* release data of rifampicin-loaded SLMs in all the batches had a higher sustained-release effect than the market brand. The *in vitro* release studies showed that, the release of rifampicin was prolonged up to more than 12 hours in both simulated intestinal fluid, pH 6.8 and phosphate buffer, pH 7.4. The order of drug release retardation with different ratios in both media was $P3 > P2 > P1$ as observed in case of LM 1:2 same for batch Q (LM 1:3). The *in vitro* drug release studies revealed that rifampicin-loaded SLMs formulated by hot homogenisation method using phospholipon 90H and *Irvingia wombolu* fat can be used to prepare sustained release dosage form for improving biopharmaceutical characteristics of rifampicin. The release mechanisms studied showed that rifampicin-loaded SLMs had mixed mechanisms of release with diffusion controlled and first-order release models as the predominant mechanism of release in all the batches.

No sustained blood level of rifampicin was evident after oral administration of the conventional rifampicin. Plasma concentration-time profile was characterized by significantly higher plasma concentration after 2 - 3 hours of administration, and then the plasma concentration declined rapidly. The *in vivo* findings revealed that the SLMs batches exhibited their absorption peak at 3 h; however, the SLMs maintained constant plasma concentration up to 18 hours. The *in vivo-in vitro* correlation studies revealed that

the formulation containing SLMs batches (P3 and Q3) had level- A correlation with a correlation coefficient of 0.916 and 0.913 respectively, thus an *in vitro* dissolution curve can serve as a surrogate for *in vivo* performance. With the Level A correlation established, it is possible that *in vitro* testing may be utilized for establishing the effects of manufacturing modifications such as minor formulation changes, manufacturing site and equipment change, alternative excipient suppliers, and a change in dosage form strength in the same formulation.

Minimum inhibitory concentrations are important in diagnostic laboratories to confirm resistance of microorganisms. Rifampicin inhibits the growth of most gram-positive bacteria as well as many gram-negative microorganisms such as *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas*, indole-positive and indole-negative *Proteus*, and *Klebsiella*. Rifampicin is very active against *Staphylococcus aureus* and coagulase-negative staphylococci. Against these organism RMP-loaded SLMs have equal activity with pure RMP at same concentration while in some at lower concentration, the formulated SLMs inhibited micro-organism at a lesser concentration, e.g. batch P3 against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* which can be termed an enhanced effect of the formulated SLMs. Rifampicin formulated SLMs retained activity and showed lowest MIC against *S. aureus*.

However, SLMs formulations could be a part of fixed dose combination, which can prevent the interaction between RMP and isoniazid (INH). Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are required to explore the clinical applicability of rifampicin-loaded microparticles particularly in presence of INH. All the prepared SLMs reflect the vital role of lipids. SLMs of rifampicin offers an attractive means of multi-particulate systems, which can be filled in standard size gelatin capsules or compressed into tablets for oral sustained release dosage forms. Further evaluation of the prepared systems *in vivo* like pharmacokinetic,

pharmacodynamic and tissue distribution studies will go a long way in establishing the therapeutic efficacy of prepared SLMs.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Calibration curve for rifampicin (SIF, pH 6.8)

Conc. (mg)	Absorbance
0.02	0.029
0.04	0.036
0.06	0.053
0.08	0.069
0.10	0.086

Calibration Curve for Rifampicin (Phosphate buffer, pH 7.4)

Conc. (mg)	Absorbance
0.02	0.036
0.04	0.071
0.06	0.095
0.08	0.132
0.10	0.160
0.12	0.196

Calibration curve for rifampicin in plasma

Conc. (μg)	Absorbance
2	0.451
4	0.589
6	1.387
8	1.547
10	1.766

Appendix 2: Particle size diameter (un-lyophilized)

Batch	Diameter			Mean particle size diameter (μm)
	A (μm)	B (μm)	C (μm)	
P1	50	24	60	45 \pm 18.58
P2	30	20	35	28 \pm 7.64
P3	60	40	50	50 \pm 10.00
P4	55	50	45	50 \pm 5.00
Q1	40	50	35	42 \pm 7.64
Q2	50	25	50	42 \pm 14.43

Q3	40	35	50	42 ± 7.64
Q4	50	65	55	57 ± 7.64

Particle size diameter (lyophilized)

Batch	Diameter			Mean Diameter (µm)
	A(µm)	B (µm)	C (µm)	
P1	25	30	40	32 ± 7.64
P2	60	55	45	53 ± 7.64
P3	45	30	35	37 ± 7.64
P4	55	40	30	42 ± 12.58
Q1	85	45	35	55 ± 26.46
Q2	65	30	35	43 ± 18.93
Q3	55	50	45	50 ± 5.00
Q4	60	30	45	45 ± 15.00

Time dependent pH stability studies

Batch	pH			
	24 hrs	1 weeks	1 month	3months
P1	5.3 ± 0.07	5.2 ± 0.14	5.2 ± 0.00	5.2 ± 0.14
P2	5.2 ± 0.07	5.3 ± 0.07	5.4 ± 0.07	5.3 ± 0.00
P3	5.3 ± 0.14	5.0 ± 0.28	4.8 ± 0.28	4.6 ± 0.10
P4	5.7 ± 0.21	5.8 ± 0.07	5.7 ± 0.07	5.4 ± 0.28
Q1	5.2 ± 0.14	5.4 ± 0.14	5.7 ± 0.07	5.6 ± 0.07
Q2	5.4 ± 0.21	5.1 ± 0.21	4.6 ± 0.00	4.8 ± 0.21
Q3	5.2 ± 0.00	5.3 ± 0.07	5.4 ± 0.35	5.4 ± 0.14
Q4	5.4 ± 0.07	5.3 ± 0.14	5.1 ± 0.14	5.2 ± 0.00

Percentage Yield of Microparticles

Batch	Weight of SLMs, w ₁ (g)	Weight of drug, w ₂ (g)	Weight of excipient, w ₃ (g)	Total theoretical weight (g)	Percentage yield (%)
P1	4.42	0.5	5.53	6.03	73.3
P2	5.38	1.0	5.53	6.53	82.5
P3	5.76	1.25	5.53	6.78	85.0
P4	3.82	0	5.53	5.53	69.1
Q1	5.31	0.5	5.53	6.03	88.1
Q2	5.52	1.0	5.53	6.53	84.6

Q3	5.36	1.25	5.53	6.78	79.1
Q4	4.76	0	5.53	5.53	86.2

Drug loading capacity

Batch	Amount of API encapsulated (mg)	Weight of lipid (mg)	Loading capacity (%)
P1	0.8	5.0	16.9
P2	1.7	5.0	34.7
P3	2.3	5.0	45.8
Q1	0.8	5.0	16.6
Q2	1.7	5.0	33.8
Q3	2.2	5.0	43.5

Stability of lyophilized rifampicin loaded SLMs in simulated gastrointestinal fluid (SGF)

Time (mins)	Abs. (RMP)	Concn, RMP (mg)	Abs. P3	Concn, P3 (mg)	Abs. Q3	Concn, Q3 (mg)
15	0.606	6.90	0.539	6.14	0.812	9.25
30	0.548	6.24	0.522	5.95	0.788	8.97
60	0.530	6.04	0.518	5.90	0.763	8.69
90	0.516	5.88	0.518	5.90	0.753	8.58
120	0.495	5.64	0.512	5.83	0.751	8.55
150	0.387	4.41	0.502	5.72	0.701	7.98
180	0.374	4.26	0.498	5.67	0.696	7.93
Decomposition		2.64		0.47		1.32
Percentage Decomposition		38.3		7.6		14.3

Encapsulation efficiency (EE %)

Batch	Absorbance		Mean absorbance	Drug content (% ± SD)	Encapsulation efficiency (%)
	A	B			
P1	0.713	0.743	0.728	0.85 ± 0.02	84.7
P2	0.722	0.770	0.746	1.73 ± 0.03	86.7
P3	0.773	0.803	0.788	2.29 ± 0.02	91.6
Q1	0.705	0.721	0.713	0.83 ± 0.01	82.9
Q2	0.700	0.754	0.727	1.69 ± 0.04	84.5
Q3	0.725	0.771	0.748	2.17 ± 0.03	87.0

Appendix 3: Micromeritic properties of lyophilized particles

Bulk density

Batch	Mass of powder (g)	Bulk volume (vb)	Bulk density (g/ml)
P1	3	12.5	0.240 ± 0.57
P2	3	15.0	0.200 ± 0.42
P3	3	13.0	0.231 ± 0.28
Q1	3	15.0	0.200 ± 0.42
Q2	3	13.0	0.231 ± 0.14
Q3	3	11.5	0.261 ± 0.57

Tapped density

Batch	Mass of particle (g)	Tapped volume (ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)
P1	3	9.0	0.333 ± 0.14
P2	3	11.0	0.273 ± 0.28
P3	3	9.5	0.316 ± 0.28
Q1	3	13.0	0.231 ± 0.57
Q2	3	10.0	0.300 ± 0.85
Q3	3	9.5	0.316 ± 0.14

Carr's compressibility index

Batch	Bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)	Carr's index (%)
P1	0.240	0.333	27.993
P2	0.200	0.273	26.659
P3	0.231	0.316	26.916
Q1	0.200	0.231	13.345
Q2	0.231	0.300	23.067
Q3	0.261	0.316	17.384

Hausner's quotient

Batch	Bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)	Hausner's ratio
P1	0.240	0.333	1.389
P2	0.200	0.273	1.364
P3	0.231	0.316	1.368

Q1	0.200	0.231	1.154
Q2	0.231	0.300	1.300
Q3	0.261	0.316	1.210

Flow rate (height: 7.5 cm, orifice diameter: 1.2 cm)

Batch	Mass of powder (g)	Time (secs)		Mean time (secs)	Flow rate (g/s)
		A	B		
P1	3.0	43.74	53.91	48.83	0.06 ± 7.19
P2	3.0	58.38	60.30	59.34	0.05 ± 1.36
P3	3.0	49.77	50.12	49.95	0.06 ± 0.25
Q1	3.0	18.71	20.95	19.83	0.15 ± 1.58
Q2	3.0	53.24	56.30	54.77	0.05 ± 2.16
Q3	3.0	58.79	59.23	59.01	0.05 ± 0.31

Angle of repose (dynamic)

Batch	Mass of powder (g)	Radius (cm)	Height of SLMs (cm)	Angle of repose (°)
P1	3.0	3.7	2.5	34.06 ± 0.85
P2	3.0	3.8	2.2	30.41 ± 0.28
P3	3.0	3.3	2.3	35.30 ± 0.14
Q1	3.0	3.0	1.0	18.42 ± 0.42
Q2	3.0	3.3	2.4	36.43 ± 0.28
Q3	3.0	3.7	2.3	31.88 ± 0.57

Appendix 4: Release studies

Sample P1, *In-vitro* release (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.043	0.039	0.041	0.467	11.4
0.5	0.059	0.057	0.058	0.661	16.1
0.75	0.071	0.075	0.073	0.831	20.3
1	0.082	0.086	0.084	0.957	23.3
2	0.098	0.102	0.100	1.139	27.8
3	0.116	0.120	0.118	1.344	32.8
4	0.122	0.126	0.124	1.412	34.4
5	0.126	0.130	0.128	1.458	35.6

6	0.136	0.130	0.133	1.515	36.9
7	0.159	0.153	0.156	1.777	43.3
8	0.184	0.190	0.187	2.130	51.9
9	0.221	0.227	0.224	2.551	62.2
10	0.232	0.234	0.233	2.654	64.7
11	0.250	0.248	0.249	2.836	69.2
12	0.264	0.262	0.263	2.995	73.1

Sample P2, *In-vitro* release (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.046	0.050	0.048	0.547	7.2
0.5	0.076	0.080	0.078	0.888	11.7
0.75	0.094	0.090	0.092	1.048	13.8
1	0.126	0.122	0.124	1.412	18.6
2	0.160	0.154	0.157	1.788	23.5
3	0.200	0.194	0.197	2.244	29.5
4	0.219	0.225	0.222	2.528	33.3
5	0.250	0.256	0.253	2.882	37.9
6	0.292	0.282	0.287	3.269	43.0
7	0.329	0.319	0.324	3.690	48.6
8	0.382	0.372	0.377	4.294	56.5
9	0.400	0.404	0.402	4.579	60.2
10	0.432	0.436	0.434	4.943	65.0
11	0.440	0.444	0.442	5.034	66.2
12	0.453	0.449	0.451	5.137	67.6

Sample P3, *In-vitro* release (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.013	0.007	0.010	0.114	1.2
0.5	0.050	0.044	0.047	0.535	5.8
0.75	0.065	0.071	0.068	0.774	8.4
1	0.121	0.127	0.124	1.412	15.4
2	0.171	0.175	0.173	1.970	21.4
3	0.200	0.196	0.198	2.255	24.5
4	0.264	0.268	0.266	3.030	32.9

5	0.281	0.285	0.283	3.223	35.0
6	0.301	0.299	0.300	3.417	37.1
7	0.311	0.309	0.310	3.531	38.4
8	0.340	0.342	0.341	3.884	42.2
9	0.409	0.413	0.411	4.681	50.9
10	0.494	0.498	0.496	5.649	61.4
11	0.513	0.509	0.511	5.820	63.3
12	0.541	0.537	0.539	6.139	66.7

Sample Q1, *In-vitro* release (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.013	0.009	0.011	0.125	3.1
0.5	0.028	0.018	0.023	0.262	6.4
0.75	0.037	0.047	0.042	0.478	11.7
1	0.077	0.087	0.082	0.934	22.8
2	0.118	0.128	0.123	1.401	34.2
3	0.136	0.130	0.133	1.515	36.9
4	0.155	0.149	0.152	1.731	42.2
5	0.196	0.202	0.199	2.267	55.3
6	0.216	0.222	0.219	2.494	60.8
7	0.247	0.241	0.244	2.779	67.8
8	0.277	0.273	0.275	3.132	76.4
9	0.303	0.299	0.301	3.428	83.6
10	0.313	0.309	0.311	3.542	86.4
11	0.312	0.316	0.314	3.576	87.2
12	0.326	0.322	0.324	3.690	90.0

Sample Q2, *In-vitro* release (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.006	0.008	0.007	0.080	1.0
0.5	0.034	0.032	0.033	0.376	4.9
0.75	0.076	0.074	0.075	0.854	11.2
1	0.106	0.104	0.105	1.196	15.7
2	0.126	0.128	0.127	1.446	19.0
3	0.144	0.146	0.145	1.651	21.7

4	0.161	0.155	0.158	1.800	23.7
5	0.179	0.185	0.182	2.073	27.3
6	0.220	0.226	0.223	2.540	33.4
7	0.289	0.283	0.286	3.259	42.9
8	0.328	0.324	0.326	3.713	48.9
9	0.374	0.370	0.372	4.237	55.7
10	0.413	0.417	0.415	4.727	62.2
11	0.446	0.450	0.448	5.103	67.1
12	0.464	0.460	0.462	5.262	69.2

Sample Q3, *In-vitro* release (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.065	0.069	0.067	0.763	8.3
0.5	0.089	0.093	0.091	1.036	11.3
0.75	0.119	0.123	0.121	1.378	15.0
1	0.166	0.170	0.168	1.913	20.8
2	0.205	0.201	0.203	2.312	25.1
3	0.295	0.291	0.293	3.337	36.3
4	0.351	0.345	0.349	3.975	43.2
5	0.385	0.377	0.381	4.339	47.2
6	0.429	0.437	0.433	4.932	53.6
7	0.457	0.465	0.461	5.251	57.1
8	0.512	0.518	0.515	5.866	63.8
9	0.544	0.550	0.547	6.230	67.7
10	0.565	0.571	0.568	6.469	70.3
11	0.575	0.581	0.578	6.583	71.6
12	0.578	0.584	0.581	6.617	71.9

Sample P1, *In-vitro* release (Phosphate Buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.049	0.053	0.051	0.313	7.6
0.5	0.087	0.083	0.085	0.521	12.7
0.75	0.127	0.123	0.125	0.767	18.7
1	0.173	0.177	0.175	1.074	26.2
2	0.283	0.287	0.285	1.748	42.6

3	0.328	0.324	0.326	2.000	48.8
4	0.383	0.377	0.380	2.331	56.9
5	0.435	0.429	0.432	2.650	64.6
6	0.495	0.489	0.492	3.018	73.6
7	0.510	0.516	0.513	3.147	76.8
8	0.531	0.537	0.534	3.276	79.9
9	0.544	0.548	0.546	3.350	81.7
10	0.545	0.541	0.543	3.331	81.3
11	0.552	0.548	0.550	3.374	82.3
12	0.544	0.540	0.542	3.325	81.1

Sample P2, *In-vitro* release (Phosphate Buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.195	0.189	0.192	1.178	15.5
0.5	0.315	0.309	0.312	1.914	25.2
0.75	0.351	0.345	0.348	2.135	28.1
1	0.371	0.365	0.368	2.258	29.7
2	0.499	0.493	0.496	3.043	40.0
3	0.635	0.629	0.632	3.877	51.0
4	0.759	0.757	0.758	4.650	61.2
5	0.805	0.803	0.804	4.933	64.9
6	0.829	0.827	0.828	5.080	66.8
7	0.890	0.886	0.888	5.448	71.7
8	0.894	0.890	0.892	5.472	72.0
9	0.930	0.926	0.928	5.693	74.9
10	0.928	0.920	0.924	5.669	74.6
11	0.939	0.931	0.935	5.736	75.5
12	0.947	0.939	0.943	5.785	76.1

Sample P3, *In-vitro* release (Phosphate Buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.150	0.152	0.151	0.926	10.1
0.5	0.263	0.265	0.264	1.620	17.6
0.75	0.377	0.379	0.378	2.319	25.2
1	0.478	0.476	0.477	2.926	31.8

2	0.567	0.565	0.566	3.472	37.7
3	0.615	0.609	0.612	3.755	40.8
4	0.723	0.717	0.720	4.417	48.0
5	0.790	0.796	0.793	4.865	52.9
6	0.837	0.843	0.840	5.153	56.0
7	0.897	0.891	0.894	5.485	59.6
8	0.903	0.899	0.901	5.528	60.1
9	0.917	0.921	0.919	5.638	61.3
10	0.961	0.965	0.963	5.908	64.2
11	0.976	0.972	0.974	5.975	65.0
12	0.995	0.991	0.993	6.092	66.2

Sample Q1, *In-vitro* release (Phosphate Buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.073	0.069	0.071	0.436	10.6
0.5	0.142	0.138	0.140	0.859	20.9
0.75	0.191	0.187	0.189	1.160	28.3
1	0.204	0.208	0.206	1.264	30.8
2	0.273	0.277	0.275	1.687	41.1
3	0.333	0.327	0.330	2.025	49.4
4	0.376	0.370	0.373	2.288	55.8
5	0.428	0.422	0.425	2.607	63.6
6	0.450	0.456	0.453	2.779	67.8
7	0.457	0.461	0.459	2.816	68.7
8	0.479	0.475	0.477	2.926	71.4
9	0.482	0.478	0.480	2.945	71.8
10	0.490	0.482	0.486	2.982	72.7
11	0.505	0.497	0.501	3.074	75.0
12	0.506	0.514	0.510	3.129	76.3

Sample Q2, *In-vitro* release (Phosphate Buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.139	0.133	0.136	0.834	11.0
0.5	0.206	0.200	0.203	1.245	16.4
0.75	0.220	0.214	0.217	1.331	17.5

1	0.250	0.256	0.253	1.552	20.4
2	0.319	0.325	0.322	1.975	26.0
3	0.362	0.366	0.364	2.233	29.4
4	0.424	0.420	0.422	2.589	34.1
5	0.480	0.476	0.478	2.933	38.6
6	0.526	0.530	0.528	3.239	42.6
7	0.587	0.585	0.586	3.595	47.3
8	0.643	0.645	0.644	3.951	52.0
9	0.724	0.726	0.725	4.448	58.5
10	0.756	0.758	0.757	4.644	61.1
11	0.800	0.804	0.802	4.920	64.7
12	0.858	0.854	0.856	5.252	69.1

Sample Q3, *In-vitro* release (Phosphate Buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (Hrs)	Absorbance			Amount Released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.116	0.122	0.119	0.730	7.9
0.5	0.248	0.250	0.249	1.528	16.6
0.75	0.352	0.354	0.353	2.166	23.5
1	0.475	0.473	0.474	2.908	31.6
2	0.565	0.563	0.564	3.460	37.6
3	0.676	0.668	0.672	4.123	44.8
4	0.756	0.748	0.752	4.613	50.1
5	0.824	0.832	0.828	5.080	55.2
6	0.857	0.865	0.861	5.282	57.4
7	0.918	0.912	0.915	5.613	61.0
8	0.926	0.920	0.923	5.663	61.5
9	0.930	0.936	0.933	5.724	62.2
10	0.947	0.943	0.945	5.798	63.0
11	0.970	0.966	0.968	5.939	64.6
12	0.979	0.983	0.981	6.018	65.4

In vitro release, branded rifampicin A (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (hrs)	Absorbance			Amount released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.334	0.349	0.342	3.89	38.9
0.5	0.533	0.534	0.534	6.08	60.8

0.75	0.667	0.659	0.663	7.55	75.5
1	0.767	0.759	0.763	8.69	86.9
2	0.826	0.819	0.823	9.37	93.7
3	0.845	0.848	0.847	9.64	96.4

In vitro release, branded rifampicin B (SIF, pH 6.8)

Time (hrs)	Absorbance			Amount released (mg)	Percentage Release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.312	0.317	0.315	3.58	35.8
0.5	0.513	0.524	0.519	5.91	59.1
0.75	0.653	0.647	0.650	7.40	74.0
1	0.763	0.752	0.758	8.63	86.3
2	0.827	0.829	0.828	9.43	94.3
3	0.852	0.858	0.855	9.74	97.4

In vitro release, branded rifampicin A (phosphate buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (hrs)	Absorbance			Amount released (mg)	Percentage release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.473	0.467	0.470	2.88	28.8
0.5	0.756	0.766	0.761	4.67	46.7
0.75	0.975	0.976	0.976	5.98	59.8
1	1.213	1.215	1.214	7.45	74.5
2	1.356	1.367	1.362	8.35	83.5
3	1.457	1.445	1.451	8.90	89.0

In vitro release, branded rifampicin B (phosphate buffer, pH 7.4)

Time (hrs)	Absorbance			Amount released (mg)	Percentage release (%)
	A	B	Mean		
0.25	0.373	0.365	0.369	2.26	22.6
0.5	0.658	0.659	0.659	4.04	40.4
0.75	0.877	0.874	0.876	5.37	53.7
1	1.126	1.133	1.130	6.93	69.3
2	1.256	1.259	1.258	7.71	77.1
3	1.397	1.411	1.404	8.61	86.1

Appendix 5: In vivo release*In vivo* release, batch P3

Time (hrs)	Absorbance				Amount absorbed (μg)	Percentage in plasma (%)
	A	B	C	Mean		
0.5	0.105	0.102	0.106	0.104	2.760	27.6
1	0.245	0.238	0.226	0.236	6.252	62.5
3	0.322	0.33	0.324	0.325	8.607	86.1
5	0.321	0.325	0.326	0.324	8.571	85.7
8	0.314	0.342	0.326	0.327	8.660	86.6
18	0.298	0.309	0.301	0.303	8.007	80.1
24	0.263	0.312	0.253	0.276	7.302	73.0

In vivo release Q3

Time (hrs)	Absorbance				Amount absorbed (μg)	Percentage plasma (%)
	A	B	C	Mean		
0.5	0.070	0.083	0.089	0.081	2.134	21.3
1	0.153	0.165	0.173	0.164	4.330	43.3
3	0.298	0.309	0.303	0.298	7.884	78.8
5	0.289	0.321	0.306	0.305	8.078	80.8
8	0.324	0.287	0.305	0.305	8.078	80.8
18	0.263	0.312	0.253	0.276	7.302	73.0
24	0.245	0.238	0.226	0.236	6.252	62.5

In vivo release RMP

Time (hrs)	Absorbance				Amount absorbed (μg)	Percentage in plasma (%)
	A	B	C	Mean		
0.5	0.070	0.083	0.089	0.081	2.134	21.3
1	0.245	0.238	0.226	0.236	6.252	62.5
3	0.370	0.349	0.365	0.361	9.559	95.6
5	0.263	0.312	0.253	0.276	7.302	73.0
8	0.062	0.066	0.062	0.063	1.675	16.8
18	0.018	0.012	0.015	0.015	0.397	4.0
24	0.017	0.012	0.015	0.015	0.388	3.9

Appendix 6: Result of minimum inhibition determination (MIC)Test organism: *Staphylococcus aureus*

Batch	Dilutions conc. and IZD ($\mu\text{g/ml/mm}$)						
	1000	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.125
P1	25	21	19	17	15	13	11
P2	26	22	20	18	16	14	12
P3	26	23	21	19	17	15	13
Q1	26	22	20	18	16	14	12
Q2	26	21	19	17	15	13	11
Q3	26	22	20	18	16	14	12
RMP	27	22	20	19	18	16	14

Test organism: *Bacillus subtilis*

Batch	Dilutions conc. and IZD ($\mu\text{g/ml/mm}$)						
	1000	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.125
P1	14	7	5	3	+	+	+
P2	15	10	8	6	4	2	+
P3	10	8	6	4	2	+	+
Q1	10	8	6	4	2	+	+
Q2	13	9	7	5	3	1	+
Q3	14	11	9	7	5	3	1
RMP	12	8	6	4	2	+	+

+ indicates microbial growth

Test organism: *Escherichia coli*

Batch	Dilutions conc. and IZD ($\mu\text{g/ml/mm}$)						
	1000	500	250	125	62.5	31.25	15.625
P1	9	7	5	3	1	+	+
P2	10	8	6	4	2	+	+
P3	8	6	4	2	+	+	+
Q1	8	6	4	2	+	+	+
Q2	10	8	6	4	2	+	+
Q3	12	10	8	6	4	2	+
RMP	13	11	9	7	5	3	+

+ indicates microbial growth

Test organism: *Klebsiella pneumonia*

Batch	Dilutions conc. and IZD ($\mu\text{g/ml/mm}$)						
	1000	500	250	125	62.5	31.25	15.625
P1	4	2	+	+	+	+	+
P2	5	3	+	+	+	+	+
P3	4	2	+	+	+	+	+
Q1	2	+	+	+	+	+	+
Q2	4	2	+	+	+	+	+
Q3	7	5	3	+	+	+	+
RMP	8	6	4	2	+	+	+

+ indicates microbial growth